
DELIVERABLE 2.2

Methodology for pilot action design and pilot actions booklet

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1 Introduction

1.1 NEXUS: Project description, aims and objectives

The NEXUS project co-designs, implements, monitors and evaluates innovative and targeted actions aimed at bridging inclusivity gaps in nine research organisations and their respective research and innovation ecosystems, with the aim of fostering institutional change through the development of inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in intersectional and intersectoral directions. Geographical inclusiveness is also promoted through a highly context-sensitive approach to action piloting in seven Member States and in Associating Countries, covering Western, Central, Southern and South-Eastern regions. The project sets up structures in less experienced institutions to go beyond the minimum GEP requirements, as defined in the Horizon Europe eligibility criterion, through a participatory, multi-stakeholder process of solution co-creation sustained by a twinning scheme (consisting of three groups of three implementing partners, referred to as ‘twin trios’) and the delivery of tailored capacity building and training programmes. NEXUS analyses how implementing partners with newly set up GEPs perform data collection, internal assessment and the planning of GEP actions to identify areas of improvement as well as potential challenges in enhancing an inclusive approach. This analysis informs the co-design and implementation of new inclusive actions, underpinned by the principles of intersectionality and intersectorality.

An intersectional approach takes into account not only inequalities on the basis of sex and gender, but also those arising from other social identities and characteristics (such as race, age, sexual orientation, religion, socio-economic status and disability) that overlap and interact in complex systems of privilege and disadvantage. In the context of institutional change, such an approach enables a more nuanced understanding of organisational dynamics and more effective policies (for a detailed overview of the intersectional approach used in the NEXUS project, see D2.1, *Report on good practices and comparative mapping of inequalities*). An intersectoral approach recognises the importance of links between sectors and organisations. In Research & Innovation, these include universities and other RPOs, RFOs, public sector organisations, NGOs, professional associations and private companies. Intersectorality, understood as developing and strengthening partnerships among diverse actors, can enable greater impact in tackling inequalities.

Overall, NEXUS actions will enhance the research excellence of participating organisations as well as effecting institutional and cultural change that is context-sensitive, realistic and sustainable. The project is structured in three phases: (1) inclusiveness assessment, (2) solution co-creation, and (3) implementation and GEP refinement (see Figure 1). This deliverable relates to activities carried out as part of the second phase, specifically in the scope of WP2, *Analysis of inequalities and co-design of solutions*.

Figure 1: NEXUS phases

1.2 Purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable

Under the scope of T2.3, *Stakeholders engagement and solutions co-creation*, this deliverable outlines the common methodology used by NEXUS implementing partners to design 45 pilot actions (five per implementing partner, either new or advancements of existing actions) aimed at bridging inclusivity gaps in research organisations. All the actions adopt an intersectional approach, while at least two actions per partner have a strong intersectoral component. The actions will be implemented over the course of 12 months, M10-M21 (June 2024 - May 2025). The actions co-designed by the implementing partners are described in this deliverable.

Each implementing partner has a GEP working group: a group of staff members (at different levels, including decision-makers such as deans, vice-deans and heads of departments) directly involved in the drafting and implementation of the institution's GEP. NEXUS partners' teams are made up of at least some GEP working group members. Through the NEXUS project, the design and development of GEP actions is taken beyond individual GEP working groups. The NEXUS co-design process takes place in two mutually-informed strands. The first strand concerns the Open Labs. These are action-oriented co-creation workshops organised by each implementing partner with both internal and external stakeholders (such as academic/research/administrative staff and students as well as RPOs, RFOs, private companies, professional associations, civil society representatives, NGOs and public bodies), to propose specific actions based on gaps and inequalities previously identified in NEXUS activities. The results of the Open Labs enable each institution's GEP working group to design concrete transformative actions to bridge inclusivity gaps. The second strand of the co-design process concerns the twin trios, three groups of three implementing partners who conduct a collaborative process to jointly design at least three actions to be implemented in each institution. The development of solutions integrates intersectional, intersectoral and geographical inclusivity as defined by the NEXUS project.

Section 2 of this deliverable presents the methodology used for the design of pilot actions. Section 3 reports on the co-creation process, while Section 4 outlines the 45 actions designed by the implementing partners.

1.3 Relation to other tasks and work packages

The methodology and actions presented in this deliverable as part of T2.3 are vital components of the NEXUS project and link to the other tasks in WP2. The co-designed actions are based on extensive analysis carried out as part of T2.1, *Analysis of good practices and existing GEPs to strengthen inclusiveness*, and T2.2, *Analysing inequalities*. These steps resulted in the identification of good practices, dimensions for the adoption of an inclusive approach, and strengths and weaknesses of the implementing partners' existing GEPs. The results of these steps were then used to inform the development of innovative and targeted actions by the partners.

This deliverable is deeply interconnected with WP3, *Pilot actions implementation, evaluation and GEPs refinement*. The co-design methodology was planned hand-in-hand with the NEXUS monitoring and evaluation methodology (presented in D3.1, *Monitoring and evaluation methodology*, as part of T3.2, *Monitoring, evaluation and ongoing redesign*) with reference to the same tools, so as to ensure coherent continuation from design to implementation, monitoring and evaluation. The actions described in this deliverable will be implemented in T3.1, *Inclusive pilot actions implementation*.

This deliverable is also strongly linked with WP4, *Capacity-building, mutual learning and knowledge sharing*. T4.1, *Ongoing support and capacity building*, provided the training for implementing partners to carry out the Open Labs and co-design of actions, and T4.2, *NEXUS Twinning Programme*, provided the structure for the mutual learning which takes place in the context of nine twinning study visits.

The actions co-designed, as well as the co-design process, will be presented by means of online and offline communication and dissemination activities delivered as part of WP5, *Impact*.

2 Methodology for pilot action design

2.1 Methodological background

2.1.1 What is co-design?

Co-design, as defined by Zamenopoulos and Alexiou (2018), is a collaborative research approach in which individuals combine their knowledge, skills, and resources to carry out design tasks. Co-design is based on the belief that everyone possesses creativity and expertise in their own experiences. This collaborative process involves multiple stakeholders working together to devise creative solutions to shared challenges (Goldet, 2000). The concept of ‘co-design’ focuses on the design process, while the concept of ‘co-creation’ includes collaborative implementation (Masterson et al. 2022). While acknowledging this difference, when applying these notions to institutional/organisational change processes, such as is the case in the NEXUS project, the boundaries between the two are blurred. It is expected that several participants/stakeholders in co-design activities (the Open Labs), both internal and external to the implementing partner institutions, will also be involved in implementing the co-designed actions. For this reason, in this deliverable and throughout the NEXUS project, we interchangeably refer to co-design and co-creation.

The co-design approach proves valuable in tackling complex issues involving diverse actors with varied expertise, while also empowering stakeholders by involving them in shaping their environment. Specifically, co-design aims to envision and implement actions aimed at improving the future by addressing specific problems. According to Zamenopoulos and Alexiou (2018), co-design involves understanding, interpreting, and addressing present challenges to create a better future through conceptual development and the creation of various elements such as spaces, products, services, or policies. In essence, co-design involves collaboratively framing and comprehending existing challenges within a particular context, with the goal of realising a desirable future. This necessitates agreement on what constitutes a desirable future. Co-design is a collaborative and participatory process that enables stakeholders to navigate complex challenges, envision a preferable future, and devise practical solutions to achieve that future. One distinguishing aspect of co-design is the utilisation of specialised tools to facilitate creativity and collaboration.

Several benefits of co-design are highlighted in resources such as the [Community of practice co-creation toolkit](#) as part of the ACT project (2021) and the [Co-design best practice report](#) as part of the CO-CREATE project (2017):

- **Diversity:** co-creation allows for the inclusion of a diverse range of actors, knowledge, hierarchical levels, and sectors in the design process.
- **Collaboration:** co-creation equips various stakeholders with tools to collaborate effectively towards a shared goal.
- **Creativity:** collective solutions generated by diverse actors tend to be more imaginative than those proposed by individuals working in isolation.

- **Network:** collaborating with diverse actors can foster enduring synergies, leading to structural change through sustained connections and collaborations.
- **Empowerment:** direct participation of different stakeholders enables them to take ownership of their environment, particularly those who might not typically be consulted in other circumstances.

Co-design also implicates some risks that can be summarised as follows:

- **Unclear objectives:** when the objectives of a co-design process are not clearly defined or communicated to all participants, it can lead to confusion, divergent interpretations, and ultimately, ineffective outcomes. To mitigate this risk, it is crucial to establish clear and measurable objectives from the outset, ensuring alignment among all stakeholders and providing a roadmap for the co-design process.
- **Going beyond feasibility:** in the enthusiasm of collaboration, there is a risk of generating ideas or solutions that are technically or economically unfeasible. It is essential to balance ideation with feasibility assessments to ensure that proposed designs can be realistically implemented within constraints such as budget, time, and available resources.
- **Raising expectations and leaving them unmet:** co-design processes have the potential to generate high expectations among stakeholders regarding the outcomes and impact of the project. However, if these expectations are not managed or tempered with realistic assessments of what can be achieved, there is a risk of disappointment and disillusionment. To address this risk, it is essential to set realistic expectations from the beginning, communicate transparently about progress and challenges, and actively involve stakeholders to foster ownership and understanding of the project's limitations.
- **Lack of transparency and accountability:** transparency and accountability are essential for building trust and maintaining the integrity of the co-design process. Without transparency regarding decision-making processes, access to information, and accountability mechanisms, there is a risk of perceptions of favouritism, bias, or exclusion among participants. To mitigate this risk, it is important to establish transparent communication channels, document decision-making processes, and hold all participants accountable for their contributions and commitments throughout the project lifecycle.

By proactively addressing these risks and incorporating appropriate safeguards and strategies into the co-design process, organisations can enhance its effectiveness, foster collaboration, and maximise the likelihood of achieving successful outcomes.

2.1.2 The programme theory and logic model

In the framework of the NEXUS project, the design of actions and their monitoring and evaluation both rely on the programme theory approach. A programme theory is “the construction of a plausible and sensible model of how a programme is supposed to work” (Bickman, 1987, p. 5). It does not refer to a single theory, but rather to one developed for each programme action. The logic model is a management tool used to structure the key elements of an action and identify the causal relationships between them, providing the grounds to plan, implement, monitor and

evaluate an intervention (OECD, 2023). The logic model represents the programme theory in terms of inputs/resources, activities, outputs, outcomes and impact of an action (Funnell & Rogers, 2011; Knowlton & Philips, 2012; Savaya & Waysman, 2005). Figure 2 presents the structure of logic models (Knowlton & Philips, 2012; Sangiuliano & Schredl, 2021; Savaya & Waysman, 2005; UN Women, 2015).

Figure 2: Structure of the logic model

The logic model works as a process. For instance: “**if** research organisations regularly hold gender bias training among all staff members (activity and output), **then** the training participants’ awareness of gender biases increases (outcomes). **Then, that leads to** a reduction in gender biases in recruitment processes (impact)”. Further details regarding the Programme theory and its application in monitoring and evaluation are provided in D3.1.

2.2 Co-design in the NEXUS project

As part of the NEXUS project, each implementing partner designs and implements five new actions (or advancements of existing GEP actions). The design of the actions takes place at three different levels:

- **Open Labs level:** took place at the initial stage of the design process (March to May 2024). Taking the gaps and inequalities identified in WP2 into account, the Open Labs identified key objectives and co-designed potential actions. The design process continues after the Open Labs, as actions are refined/finalised either in the frame of the twin trios or at the institutional level;
- **Twin trios level:** at least three out of the five actions were co-designed in the frame of an ad hoc study visit in April 2024. Ideas/input on these three actions could come (but not necessarily) from the results of the Open Labs;
- **Institutional level:** the finalisation of the design of all the five actions happened at institutional level by the end of May 2024. Even the actions jointly designed in the twin trios required adaptation by each institution to some extent.

Figure 3: NEXUS co-design process

The actions designed were required to have the following features, according to the Grant Agreement:

- All the developed actions need to adopt an intersectional approach;
- At least two out of the five actions have to have a strong intersectoral component (foresee the collaboration with external stakeholders);
- At least one out of the five actions must concern inclusive data collection processes in place at institutional level (taking into consideration the methodology outlined in section 6 of D2.1).

2.2.1 Co-design support

As part of WP2 and WP4, Smart Venice (SV) conducted several activities to support implementing partners throughout the co-design process. In the frame of T2.3, SV developed guidelines for implementing partners on how to plan and carry out the Open Labs. Similarly, as part of T4.2, SV prepared guidelines on how to continue the co-design process in the context of the first study visit as part of the twinning programme. Both sets of guidelines (the contents of which are embedded in the following three sections) were accompanied by the respective reporting templates (see Annex 4 and Annex 5, respectively). SV also prepared consent forms to be used with stakeholders participating in the Open Labs (see Annex 2), and offered bilateral support to implementing partners.

The guidelines on how to carry out the Open Labs were presented to the implementing partners in an ad-hoc train-the-multipliers session on 15 February 2024, as part of T4.1, covering an introduction of the co-design process and NEXUS framework, the goals, target and methodology of the Open Labs, tools and instructions for the co-design of actions, the reporting template, and group work to solidify knowledge acquired on co-designing actions.

2.2.2 Co-design in the Open Labs

What are the Open Labs?

The Open Labs are co-creation workshops that each implementing partner organised with the aim of brainstorming and identifying possible solutions/actions to be implemented, based on the findings of T2.2. Each implementing partner organised two Open Labs between March and May 2024. Each workshop lasted two to three hours. The Open Labs were preparatory to the design of the actions, which was finalised in June 2024, partly in the frame of the twin trios. The Open Labs liaise with the NEXUS Twinning Programme and make use of the same tools for designing actions.

As part of the Open Labs, implementing partners:

- Presented their own GEP and its gaps, as well as the inequalities that emerged in the frame of the previous project activities (T2.2);
- Discussed with stakeholders on the topic of inequality grounds and key objectives for new actions;
- Brainstormed possible solutions to those inequalities in terms of new actions exploring their collaborative potential, and started designing them.

The outcome of the Open Labs informed the design of the actions, two of which are to be implemented with external stakeholders (based on the Grant Agreement).

Who participated in the Open Labs?

Both internal and external stakeholders participated in the Open Labs.

Internal stakeholders included:

- Members of the GEP working group of each partner institution. In order to ensure a smooth design and implementation of the actions, the GEP working group is composed of staff of the institution at different levels, including decision makers (e.g. deans, vice-deans, heads of departments).
- Other academic, research and administrative staff, especially covering decision making roles (middle and top management).

The involvement of middle management representatives was especially valuable. Implementing partners were informed that while engaging top management positions might be beneficial, it would require careful preparation to ensure they took on a more observational role and that their presence was not perceived as imposing or intimidating to other participants.

External stakeholders, on the other hand, included the representatives of organisations with whom partners already had collaborations/projects in place, or organisations with which partners were open to collaborating with in the implementation of actions. Such organisations could be:

- Other Research Performing Organisations (RPOs);
- Research Funding Organisations (RFOs);
- Policy makers/public bodies;

- Entities of industry & business sector (e.g. companies);
- Feminist NGOs;
- Other civil society organisations;
- Professional organisations;
- Others.

With regards to external stakeholders, implementing partners were advised to pay additional attention to their engagement by considering the following:

- As the process concerned organisational/institutional change and details on potentially sensitive topics would be shared, it would be preferable if the external stakeholders involved in the Open Labs were trusted persons with whom an existing collaboration was in place. These would ideally be entities/persons who were interested in working on, or had already committed to, gender equality and who acknowledged the value of exploring possible synergies on the topic. For new contacts, it was suggested to have a preparatory call/meeting to better explore their views on the topics at stake and have a preliminary understanding of potential areas for collaboration on gender equality issues.
- It would be preferable if external stakeholders were asked in advance to position themselves in the role of 'observers' in case any sensitive and/or controversial issues arose, especially in the initial phase, where the organisation's gaps/inequalities/challenges were explored. Here, their input could consist, for example, in sharing similar challenges and the way they have tackled them. Alternatively, partners could consider the option to invite external stakeholders to the second part of the co-design process only, where the focus would be more concrete and go deeper into the design of specific actions (see methodology below).
- Implementing partners were advised to explain the presence of external stakeholders to the other participants by referring to the intersectoral inclusiveness feature of the NEXUS project and its aim of promoting synergies at the Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem level.

Partners strategically invited stakeholders depending on the identified gaps and areas they envisioned focusing on. The methodology suggested that between 10 and 15 people participate in the Open Labs (ideally the same people in the two workshops), with 30% representing external stakeholders. The template used by implementing partners to invite external stakeholders to take part in the Open Labs is available in Annex 1. Annex 2 contains the consent form used with both internal and external stakeholders.

Methodology

Led by each GEP working group, two Open Lab workshops were organised at each implementing partner organisation to discuss the outcomes from T2.2 as well as to support the identification of five inclusive actions.

The two workshops had two different purposes:

1. The first workshop reviewed the results delivered in T2.2 in terms of gaps and inequalities (D2.1) and discussed grounds of inequality to focus on and identify key objectives in terms of inclusiveness in broader terms.

2. The second workshop aimed at co-designing a portfolio of potential inclusive actions.

Participatory design thinking was used to ensure broad involvement of the various stakeholders. The results of the workshops helped each institution’s GEP working group to design concrete transformative actions to bridge the identified gaps and inequalities.

Two scenarios, outlined below, were envisaged.

Scenario 1

For partners who opted for the first (preferable) scenario, an internal intermediate meeting within the GEP working group took place between the two workshops to validate the grounds of inequality and the key objectives, and to identify a minimum of three actions to co-design in the frame of the second workshop. This aimed to ensure that the GEP working group received approval by the management of the institution about the key objectives and the concrete actions to be co-designed during the second workshop, strengthening the role of the co-design process itself. More details are provided in the paragraph *Meeting between the first and the second workshop*.

Figure 4: Co-design process in Scenario 1

Scenario 2

In case an intermediate meeting within the GEP working group and the approval by the management before the second workshop was not feasible, the process was more open and the decision on specific actions was made at the end of the co-design process.

Figure 5: Co-design process in Scenario 2

1st workshop – Agenda, methods and activities

This section presents the agenda, the methods and the contents of the first workshop, which could be slightly adapted by partners.

Time	Activity n.	Activity description	Notes
20 minutes		Welcome and round table of introductions	
10 minutes	First activity	Brief introduction of the NEXUS project and agenda of the two workshops	A few slides need to be prepared by partner to present the project.
20 minutes	Second activity	Presentation of the Institution's GEP Q&A session	Each partner presents their own GEP, highlighting its objectives, areas of intervention and specific actions included with the level of advancement. Q&A session follows.
20 minutes	Third activity	GEP's gaps and inequalities – presentation of results of T2.2 Q&A session	Each partner presents the gaps and inequalities emerging from the analysis conducted in T2.2. (see more details below).
15 minutes		Coffee break	
30 minutes	Fourth activity	Brainstorming on inequality grounds – group work part 1	Depending on the number of people participating, two or three groups of around five people each are created to discuss on inequality grounds (see more details below).

35 minutes	Fifth activity	Identifying key objectives – group work part 2	Still divided in groups, participants discuss the key objectives (see more details below).
20 minutes		Reporting in plenary	Each group reports in plenary about the results of the previous two activities.
10 minutes		Closing and agenda of the second session	

Table 1: Agenda for the first workshop

First and second activities

As shown in the agenda above, the first workshop included a first part for introducing the project as well as presenting the GEP to stakeholders, as both internal and external stakeholders might not be aware of the specific content of the institution’s GEP.

Third activity

The workshop then continued with a presentation concerning the GEP’s gaps and inequalities (although this could be embedded in the previous presentation, if preferable). In this slot, each partner presented the gaps and inequalities emerging from the assessment conducted in T2.2, as reported in D2.1. In particular, it was suggested to focus on the following contents:

- Gender gaps in terms of horizontal and vertical segregation (D2.1, section 2.2.1);
- Other existing equality, diversity and inclusion issues present in the institution (D2.1, section 2.2.2);
- Intersectionality aspects and gaps (D2.1, sections 2.2.3 and 5.2.3);
- Gaps in domains addressed (D2.1, section 5.2.4);
- Current data collection system: inequalities and domains addressed (D2.1, sections 5.1.1, 5.1.2 and 5.1.4), external stakeholders in data collection (D2.1, section 5.1.3) and gaps, obstacles and areas of improvement for inclusive data collection (of D2.1, section 5.1.9).

Each partner reported on the gaps/issues in relation to their own organisation.

Fourth activity

After a coffee break, the participants were split into two or three groups of around five people each. It was recommended to create balanced groups in terms of:

- Gender (and intersected axes of difference, if visible/explicit);
- Roles in the institution;
- Internal and external stakeholders.

The activity consisted in an open discussion which, based on the gaps and inequalities presented in the third activity, touched on the following points:

- Inequality grounds (besides gender) that are considered particularly relevant at the national level. In particular, participants reflected on which minorities are particularly represented in their country. Examples of inequality grounds are: age, gender identity, sexual orientation, ethnicity, disability, socio-economic background;

- Minoritised groups in the institution. It was not necessary for these groups to be officially tracked through data collection; the reflection could be based on observations/informal knowledge channels;
- Inequality grounds to be tackled in the new actions. Preliminary reflections coming from the twinning group could be shared during the discussion.

The overall goal of the exercise was to reach a consensus among participants on the inequality grounds that are considered important and feasible to tackle, and to report them in the template (Table 2) that would also be used during the fifth activity. An intersectional approach was applied, meaning that other inequality grounds (beyond gender) needed to be tackled as they intersect with gender, not as stand-alone categories. At the same time, gender needed to be kept as a core dimension.

Each group was guided in the activity by a facilitator, who also kept track of time. A note taker was also identified. Facilitators could also cover the role of note takers.

Fifth activity

Once the inequality grounds were explored and a preliminary agreement was reached on the ones to tackle in the frame of the new actions, the workshop continued with the identification of key objectives for each thematic area. These are the long-term goals with an impact within the organisation and beyond. Key objectives can be measurable. Examples of key objectives for each thematic area were provided:

1. **Work-life balance and organisational culture:** e.g., more flexibility in working hours for care givers.
2. **Leadership and decision making:** e.g., decision making bodies balanced in terms of gender and ethnic background.
3. **Recruitment and career progression:** e.g., more diversity in the new staff hired in terms of gender and other minorities.
4. **Research and teaching content:** e.g., integration of gender and intersectional aspects in most of teaching curricula.
5. **Measures against gender-based violence (GBV) including sexual harassment:** e.g., decrease of cases of GBV and sexual harassment reported by students and staff of all genders.

Partners could either decide to make groups work on all five areas, or on a selected few. It was suggested to conduct the activity as a brainstorming with the support of a whiteboard or a poster organised in the five areas of intervention mentioned above. In case the workshop was held online, the use of collaborative tools such as Mural, Miro or shared Google Docs was recommended. Five minutes were allocated per intervention area.

Below is an example of the template provided to partners in two versions. The first version is empty, while the second provides an example of how the template could be filled after the brainstorming within the groups.

	Identified gap/inequality	Inequality grounds	Thematic area	Key objectives
1				
2				
3				

Table 2: Empty template for the fifth activity

	Identified gap/inequality	Inequality grounds	Thematic area	Key objectives
1	5% of women in boards/committees	Gender, age	Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	Understand and remove barriers to participation Achieve a 20% of women representation in the next five years
2	20% of girls enrolled in STEM courses, 2% with ethnic/migrant background	Gender, race and ethnicity, social class	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content	Increase collaboration with high schools in the region Make STEM curricula known and attractive for girls including from vulnerable communities
3	Plus 20% reported episodes of harassment on campus	Gender, gender identity, and sexual orientation	Measures against GBV including sexual harassment	Increase knowledge on current situation Create internal engagement and ownership of the problem Put concrete measures in place

Table 3: Example of a filled template for the fifth activity

Meeting between the first and the second workshop

In case the first scenario was adopted, each institution's GEP working group met in the time frame between the first and second workshop to reflect internally on the results of the first workshop, particularly in terms of inequality grounds and key objectives identified, and also to prepare the second workshop.

In particular, the GEP working group:

- Validated the inequality grounds identified during the first workshop;
- Went through the key objectives that emerged, selecting and eventually refining the ones that could be further developed and translated them into concrete actions - anything that had already emerged from the twin trios also had to be taken into consideration;
- Identified at least three actions which could reach the key objectives selected and that would be co-designed during the second workshop together with three new actions identified by workshop participants.

The three actions to be identified by the GEP working group could either be totally new actions, or advancements of existing actions in a more inclusive direction. Partners could get inspiration going through the inclusive good practices included in D2.1, sections 4.1.3 and 4.2. The goal was for the GEP working group to receive approval by the management of the institution on the key objectives and concrete actions on which the institution wanted to focus on before the second workshop, strengthening the role of the co-design.

2nd workshop – Agenda, methods and activities

This section presents the agenda, the methods and the contents of the second workshop, which could be slightly adapted by partners.

Time	Activity n.	Activity description	Notes
15 minutes		Welcome and agenda of the workshop	If different people from the previous workshop are present, another round table can take place.
20 minutes	First activity	Presentation of the results of the previous workshop, key objectives and actions identified Q&A session	During this presentation, the results of the previous workshop are briefly presented as well as the process of validation of the grounds of inequality and of the key objectives (see more details below). The ideas in terms of actions identified by the GEP working group are also explained. ¹ A Q&A session follows.
45 minutes	Second activity – part 1	Developing logic models: Action co-design group work - part 1	Depending on the number of people participating, two or three groups of around five people each is created to work on logic models (see more details below).
15 minutes		Coffee break	
45 minutes	Second activity – part 2	Actions co-design group work - part 2	
30 minutes	Third activity	Reporting in plenary	Each group reports in plenary about the results of the previous activity
10 minutes		Closing and presentation of the next steps	Facilitators of the workshop explain to participants what the next steps of the NEXUS project will be.

Table 4: Agenda for the second workshop

First activity

During this first activity, the facilitators of the workshop presented the results of the previous workshop (especially for the new participants, if any). In case Scenario 1 was adopted (with a

¹ In case Scenario 2 is adopted, during this activity only the results of the first workshop are reported.

meeting of the GEP working group between the two workshops), they also reported on this meeting and explained the inequality grounds and the key objectives the GEP working group decided to focus on, as well as ideas in terms of new actions.

Second activity

This is the core co-design activity of the whole Open Lab. The group was split preferably into three groups of four or five, with a balanced composition. Each group was assigned a key objective and an action among the ones presented in the first activity using a template inspired by the logic model. In case Scenario 1 was adopted (and a meeting with the management took place between the two workshops), each group brainstormed and designed one additional action. This additional action could respond to the same key objective assigned, or to another one among the ones identified during the first workshop.

In case Scenario 2 was adopted (and the meeting with the GEP working group between the two workshops had not yet taken place), the groups were asked to brainstorm and identified two actions to be co-designed, allowing for more options to be discussed at the meeting with management.

In case the workshop was held online, the template in Figure 6 could be replicated in an online tool (e.g. Miro, Mural), while in case of in person workshops it could be replicated on a poster or printed using the template available in Annex 3, and participants could contribute using sticky notes. Each group worked on two posters (one poster per action). A facilitator guided the exercise while another person (or the same facilitator) took notes to ensure all contributions from participants were taken into account.

Key objective:
Action's title:

Impact	
Outcomes	
Audience	
Time-frame	
Activities	
Outputs	
Inputs	
Inclusive dimensions	

Figure 6: Template for the design of actions

The group went through the different sections of the diagram focusing on impacts, outcomes, audience, outputs and inclusive dimensions. The design of an action was estimated to take 45 minutes.

Below is a grid with questions to guide the group work, explanations and examples for each step. The examples were formulated with reference to an action consisting in the organisation and delivery of training on integrating intersectionality in teaching curricula. It could be used by facilitators to better guide the activity. For each guiding question a duration is suggested. The same grid is followed for both actions.

Guiding question	Section	Explanation	Examples
To achieve what?	Impact	The impact is the expected long-term result of an action. It is the consequence of the action beyond its direct and immediate interaction with the target/audience of the	Most of the curricula of the university integrate intersectionality aspects.

(15 minutes)		action. An action can have an impact across different dimension: economic, social, technological, etc.. To measure the impact, the effects of an action should be observed over a period of time from three to five years (Sangiuliano et al, 2020).	
	Outcomes	The outcome comprises the immediate expected effects of the action on participants/audience. It usually refers to changes in attitudes, awareness, motivations, knowledge and skills, interests. Outcomes can be short-term (less than a year) or medium-term (one to two years) (Sangiuliano et al, 2020). When defining the outcomes it is helpful to make them SMART: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time Specific (Yemm, 2012) – see more details in D3.1.	Short-term outcome: increased awareness of participants of the training of the importance of integrating intersectionality in teaching curricula. Medium-term outcome: 50% of institution’s professors have been trained and are aware of the importance of integrating intersectionality in teaching curricula.
For whom? (5 minutes)	Audience	This step is about defining who is the action designed for (the participants of the action). The identification of the audience also implies thinking about their characteristics and needs.	Professors and researchers.
When? (5 minutes)	Time-frame	This is the timeframe of the action. It is the period of time in which the action is implemented (it also includes the preparatory activities).	June 2024 – November 2024.
What to do? (10 minutes)	Activities	This is about the concrete activities that will need to be carried out to achieve the goals defined. They refer to the concrete implementation of the action also from the organisational/logistic point of view.	Identify trainers, set up an agenda, set the dates of the training.
	Outputs	It is the numeric result of the activities conducted to implement the action.	Delivery of two rounds of training involving at least 20 professors per round.
With which resources? (5 minutes)	Input	This is about the resources needed to implement the activity both time-related, human, financial and material.	Two people from the institution, an external trainer. Budget to pay the trainer. Six hours for the organisation, four hours for the delivery. A dedicated room with all the needed devices and materials for collaborative activities.

Is the action inclusive? (5 minutes)	Inclusive dimensions	This step addressed the inclusive dimensions of the action in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intersectionality: different grounds of inequality tackled; - Intersectoriality: involvement of external stakeholders in the implementation of the action (collaborative action). 	The action is intersectional in the content and involves an external stakeholder in its implementation (external trainers).
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Table 5: Guiding questions for group work

It was crucial to provide participants with a clear notion of the difference between action and activity. ‘Action’ refers to the measure that will be implemented and included in the GEP, aimed at reaching the identified key objective. For instance, examples of actions can be: organisation and delivery of training on integrating intersectionality in teaching curricula, organisation of a mentoring programme, setting up of a protocol/system to report cases of GBV/sexual harassment, a communication campaign on the integration of intersectionality in research, integration of the recruitment protocols in an intersectional perspective, integration of the institution’s data collection system, etc.

On the contrary, ‘activity’ refers to the different concrete steps that need to be taken to implement the action. As reported in Table 5, in case of an action consisting in a training course, activities could be: identification of the trainers, set up of the training agenda and dates, identification of the room and preparation of the necessary materials. The level of detail in the identification of the activities to be put in place to implement an action could vary according to the action itself. In the frame of the co-design in the Open Labs, it was not expected that stakeholders would focus much on the activities, since these often depend on the internal institutional procedures that stakeholders might not be aware of.

Third activity

Each group presented the results of the design to the other groups. A plenary discussion could follow, if time allowed.

General tips for online workshops

This section is inspired by the deliverable [Co-design guidelines](#), elaborated in the frame of the CALIPER project (CALIPER, 2020). It provides some guidelines, made available to implementing partners, for ensuring smooth online workshops, adapting to the unique challenges and dynamics of virtual environments:

1. Time management

- Clearly communicate the duration of each activity to participants;
- Monitor time during activities, perhaps using alarms or online timers;
- Select activities based on the available time and avoid exceeding two consecutive hours without breaks.

2. Creating a safe space

- Establish equality among participants through icebreaker exercises or introductions;
- Clearly outline the workshop's objectives, emphasising expression of personal experiences and collaborative problem-solving;
- Establish transparent participation rules, including guidelines for microphone use, hand-raising, and chat usage;
- Encourage participants to keep their cameras on to foster engagement and connection;
- Reinforce participation rules as needed during the workshop to maintain an equitable environment.

3. Readiness for the unexpected

- Familiarise yourself with online tools and conduct tests if necessary;
- Ensure clarity on the rules of each activity to address unexpected participant inquiries;
- Prepare contingency plans for potential issues like last-minute participant absences or technical difficulties;
- Consider providing technical instructions for using the online platform beforehand to avoid time loss during the workshop;
- If feasible, involve multiple facilitators, with distinct roles such as animator, technical assistant, and observer, to enhance workshop efficiency and effectiveness.

Examples of participation rules:

- Rounds: Participants speak in turn as determined by the facilitator, with no interruptions. Microphones are activated only when speaking;
- Raise hands: Use the "raise hand" feature or physical gestures for orderly participation. Microphones are activated only when speaking;
- Open speaking: Participants contribute freely, ideal for brainstorming. Microphones can remain active unless there are technical issues.

2.2.3 Co-design in twin trios

What are the twin trios?

The Twinning Programme is a mutual learning programme that represents one of the key features of the NEXUS project. It includes interinstitutional working groups based on complementarities among partners with regards to strengths, weakness and priorities in the five GEP recommended areas (see p. 18) and in the three dimensions of inclusivity (intersectional, intersectoral and geographical).

The goal of the Twinning Programme is twofold:

1. To foster mutual learning among partners and facilitate ongoing dialogue and exchange by:
 - Leveraging good practices;
 - Sharing challenges and opportunities;
 - Linking to existing Communities of Practice and the Hubs.

2. To jointly design at least three out of five NEXUS actions and then implement them, focusing on at least two of the five recommended GEP action areas (see p. 18).

The trios work in the frame of:

1. Study visits and periodic calls;
2. Periodic thematic group discussions (helpdesk sessions organised by SV).

Twin trio composition

The trios were created starting from the results of the analysis conducted in T2.2. Based on the strengths and weaknesses emerged from the GEPs' analysis, partners were grouped in three clusters:

- Towards advancing (IIT, TUD, FredU);
- Committing (KU, AGH, UM);
- Initial steps (NU, BZN, SU).

Each partner takes part in one trio only.

Areas of intervention where the individual GEPs showed room for improvement were identified, as well as commonalities to this regard. This analysis led to the creation of the trios shown in Table 6, which were presented during the study visit in Dublin and accepted by partners. The suggested thematic areas were not binding.

Trio	Partners	Common thematic areas with room for improvement
Trio One	FredU, AGH, BZN	Areas 2 & 4 (Gender equality in leadership & decision-making; Gender equality in research and teaching content).
Trio Two	TUD, KU, UNISOFIA	Areas 4 & 5 (Gender equality in research & teaching content; Measures against GBV including sexual harassment).
Trio Three	IIT, UM, UN	Areas 1 & 4 (Worklife balance & organisational culture; Gender equality in research & teaching content).

Table 6: NEXUS twin trio composition and thematic areas

Co-design in the twin trios

In the frame of the Twinning Programme, at least three out of the five actions were co-designed by each trio during a study visit. The process began with the Dublin study visit on 31 January 2024, and further ideas/input on these three actions could derive from the results of the Open Labs, even if this was not strictly necessary and it was up to the partners and the trios to determine how to coordinate the different co-design levels.

For the co-design of the actions in the frame of the twin trios, partners used the same template used for the co-design during the Open Labs. The co-design of actions within the trios needed to tackle at least two among the five GEP thematic areas.

Trios could work with different approaches for the co-design of actions:

1. **Harmonised approach:** Three common actions are co-designed with possible institutional adaptations in terms of outputs/outcomes indicators.
2. **Flexible approach:** Nine different actions are co-designed. In this case the trios identify the same thematic areas to focus on but each partner identifies its own three specific actions, with the two other members of the trio having a support/feedback role providing ideas, spotlighting potential challenges, and ultimately playing the role of a ‘critical friend’.
3. **Mixed approach:** in this case, one-two common actions are co-designed along with other actions that are specific to one partner only. It can also be the case that one or few of the actions are common to two members of the trio only.

Twin actions could be either advancements of existing actions or entirely new ones. In the latter case, a ‘piloting/experimental’ approach could be considered, in order to avoid completely changing existing and ongoing GEPs, with the related bureaucratic issues that this might imply. A balanced approach was suggested, with both types of actions being co-designed and implemented.

Study visits

In the scope of the NEXUS project, each trio meets three times in person during three study visits to take place at each partner’s premises. Each study visit lasts one day and a half, and aims to promote mutual learning through sharing good practices as well as supporting the co-design, implementation and evaluation of the actions. The involvement of the hosting institution’s internal and external stakeholders is recommended.

Study visits are organised in a hybrid way in order to ensure the participation of more members of each institution’s GEP working group.

Table 7 presents the planned study visits. The first set of study visits among the twin trios took place between 15 April and 4 June 2024. An additional hybrid session in twin trios will be held

during the consortium meeting in Nicosia, Cyprus, on 24 - 25 September 2024. Only the first study visit focuses on co-design. As a result, only the first study visit is included in the scope of this deliverable.

Study visits	Focus	Period
First study visit	Actions’ design	M8 (April - June 2024)
Second study visit	Actions’ implementation and monitoring	M10-M15 (June - December 2024)
Third study visit	Actions’ evaluation and redesign	M16-M18 (February – mid-March 2025)

Table 7: Study visit focus and timing

While the logistical arrangements of the study visits are up to the trios, including the hosting order, it was suggested to structure the study visit in two main parts:

- **A first part dedicated to the mutual learning and sharing of good practices:** this part could include:
 - o A tour of the hosting institution showing the different areas, laboratories and meeting with relevant staff of the institution;
 - o The presentation of good practices of the hosting institution in terms of gender equality and inclusion, as well as collaboration with external stakeholders on relevant activities/projects. This could be done in different ways depending on the kind of good practices, for instance through a presentation by the NEXUS team at the hosting organisation, or by inviting persons in charge of the good practices to tell more and share their experience, or by visiting specific places of the institution if the good practice is about an event, a laboratory, an exhibition etc.
 - o The participation of external stakeholders of the innovation ecosystems to present good practices in gender equality and inclusion. External stakeholders available to participate in this session and having good practices to share could be identified in the frame of the Open Labs. This would create room for additional networking opportunities both for the engaged stakeholders and the NEXUS partners.
 - o A session in which NEXUS guest partners participating in the study visit presented their own organisation and gender equality and inclusion actions to internal and external stakeholders, students included.
- **A more hands-on second part** in which partners focused on a specific activity depending on the project stage: actions’ design, implementation, monitoring, evaluation and redesign. This component of the visit could also include a brainstorming on learning needs and challenges shared by partners. The second and the third study

visit will also include a re-design workshop based on the results of monitoring and evaluation.

Below is a draft agenda for the first study visit, which took place between April and June 2024, focused on the co-design of actions. The agenda covers one day and a half; however partners could autonomously allocate the different slots in a different order, according to the specific schedule.

Time	Activity description	Notes
30 minutes	Welcoming and round table of presentation	In this first introductory part the hosting organisation welcomes the participants and introduces the components of the GEP working group. It is suggested that the hosting organisation involves as many components of the GEP working group as possible. The involvement of members of the middle-top management is also welcome.
30 minutes - 1 hour	Hosting institution tour	In this activity, the hosting partner conducts a tour of the institution, showing the different areas, laboratories and introducing, when possible, other relevant staff of the institution.
1 hour	Institutions' good practices on gender equality and inclusion	The hosting organisation presents any good practices related to gender equality and inclusion that it has, also possibly inviting other staff to present. Also good practices related to collaborative activities/projects can be shared. This activity, depending on the kind of good practice, can take place in different ways, also by visiting specific areas of the institution. In this case it can be combined with the previous one. Q&A session follows.
1 hour	External stakeholders' good practices on gender equality and inclusion	During this activity one or more external stakeholders can intervene and present good practices on gender equality and inclusion. Q&A session follows.
1 hour and a half	Exploring guests' institutions and good practices	In this activity the focus is on the NEXUS organisations participating in the study visit. The idea is that each of the two institutions representatives talk about their own organisation, presenting its structure and features, as well as any good practice in terms of gender equality and inclusion. The ideal audience of this session are both internal stakeholders, external stakeholders and also students. Participants in this session can pose questions to the guests.
6 hours	Joint actions' co-design	This activity concerns the co-design of the three or more actions within the trios. The template shared in the T2.3 guidelines is used. Further indications for this activity are

		provided below. In this activity it is also important that other members of the guest institution can participate remotely.
1 hour	Learning needs brainstorming	During this activity the trio brainstorms about the challenges that emerged from the co-design of actions and related learning needs, reflecting on which specific knowledge/skills/capacities would be beneficial for them to develop further, in view of an optimal implementation of the actions. The outcome of this activity will feed the helpdesk programme.
30 minutes	Next steps	The trio set the next steps of the collaboration in terms of periodic calls and the following study visit.

Table 8: Agenda for the first study visit

2.2.4 Finalisation at the institutional level

The results of the Open Labs and first Twinning Programme study visit support each institution’s GEP working group to design concrete transformative actions to bridge the identified gaps and inequalities. After the workshops, the GEP working group finalised the design of the actions, continuing to work with the template provided. The design of the five actions was finalised in June 2024. The internal staff involved in the design of the actions is expected to be involved also in the evaluation of the design taking place during Evaluation and Redesign workshops in the frame of the monitoring and evaluation process (see D3.1). The finalised actions designed are included in this deliverable. In addition, when feasible, they will be incorporated in each respective GEP.

3 Co-design process

3.1 Open Labs

The Open Labs took place between the 7 March and 21 May 2024. For seven partners, the Open Labs took place before the first study visit, while for two they took place after (BZN and UM). Out of the nine implementing partners, one opted for Scenario 1 (organising an internal intermediate meeting with the GEP working group and management between the two workshops – IIT), while eight opted for Scenario 2 (the process was more open and the meeting with management took place at the end of the co-design process).

Partner	Open Lab 1				Open Lab 2			
	Date	N Participants	N externals (%)	N men (%)	Date	N Participants	N externals (%)	N men (%)
TUD	7 March	15	1 (7%)	3 (20%)	14 March	17	4 (24%)	3 (18%)
FredU	4 April	10	0 (0%)	3 (30%)	8 April	11	1 (9%)	3 (27%)
UNISOFIA	26 March	14	5 (36%)	3 (21%)	2 April	15	5 (33%)	3 (20%)
UM	16 May	14	0 (0%)	3 (21%)	21 May	4	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
AGH	10 April	12	5 (42%)	4 (33%)	10 April	12	5 (42%)	4 (33%)
BZN	25 April	12	0 (0%)	2 (17%)	29 April	12	4 (33%)	0 (0%)
UN	15 March	19	7 (37%)	9 (47%)	29 March	18	7 (39%)	7 (39%)
IIT	18 March	14	3 (21%)	3 (21%)	8 April	11	3 (27%)	2 (18%)
KU	28 March	10	4 (40%)	1 (10%)	29 March	11	4 (36%)	0 (0%)
Total		120	25 (21%)	31 (26%)		111	33 (30%)	22 (20%)

Table 9: Date, number of participants, number and share of external stakeholders, and number and share of men among participants per Open Lab workshop.

The number of participants per workshop ranged from four to 19. In total, 120 participants took part in the first workshop across the nine implementing partner institutions, while 111 took part in the second workshop. The average number of participants was 13 in the first workshop and 12 in the second workshop.

One common challenge regarded the participation of external stakeholders. The average share of external stakeholders across both Open Labs was 25% (21% in the first workshop and 30% in the second workshop). Two partner institutions involved only internal stakeholders in the first workshop (FredU and BZN), and one partner institution conducted both workshops without the participation of external stakeholders, despite having invited them (UM). Internal stakeholders who participated spanned across management, administrative, research and teaching staff, as well as student representatives. The external stakeholders who participated included representatives of feminist organisations and CSOs, RPOs and RFOs, government agencies and companies.

Gender-balanced participation was also a common challenge, with all workshops having a majority of women participants. In the second workshop the group of participants was composed entirely of women in three partner institutions (KU, BZN, UM). Overall, 77% of participants were women and 23% were men.

Multiple inequality grounds at the national and institutional level (beyond gender) were identified and discussed in the workshops. These included ethnicity, religion, disability, age, socioeconomic status, parental/family status, level of education, and sexual orientation among others.

In total, 29 actions were co-designed across the nine implementing partner institutions. Between two and six actions were co-designed per partner.

Not all partners have held meetings with management to discuss potential actions or have involved management in the co-creation process. There is variability between partners in terms of whether they received formal approval to proceed with the implementation of the selected actions. For instance, in the case of SU the actions will be approved in the Academic Council vote; for Les Mans, all actions designed were validated and will become part of the next GEP, although the budget still needs to be discussed; BZN has not had a meeting with management, although approval is expected and foreseen in the month of July. Overall, partners either received approval from the management, or plan to receive it soon, or do not need to receive a formal approval for the implementation of the actions co-designed already having a general permission in place by the top management. All partners are expected to have started the implementation of most actions by June/July 2024.

The sub-sections below contain information on the Open Lab workshops at each partner organisation, as well as the main results of the workshops. Extended reports on the Open Labs are available on the project SharePoint.

3.1.1 Technological University Dublin (TUD)

	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
Open Labs dates	7 March 2024		14 March 2024	
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	15		17	
	Women: 12	Men: 3	Women: 14	Men: 3
	Internal: 14	External: 1	Internal: 13	External: 4
Scenario adopted	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders participating	Human resources, Research Office, Research Hub, Library services, Employee engagement office, Data reporting, Academic Affairs, EDI Office, Learning Dev. A Head of Discipline, a Head of School, a research manager, professors, lecturers and researchers also attended.			

<p>Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating</p>	<p>RPOs (Maynooth University), representatives of university EDI Offices (Trinity College Dublin, Royal College of Surgeons Ireland, Klagenfurt University Austria).</p>
<p>Main results of the first workshop</p>	<p>Participants were divided into two groups and discussed issues related to data collection, GEP implementation, and identified key objectives.</p> <p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All nine inequality grounds that are recognised in Ireland (gender, marital status, family status, age, disability, sexual orientation, race, religion, and membership of the Traveler community). <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture: To be able to properly implement current Athena Swan actions on supporting people upon return from maternity leave. Bereavement leave/compassionate leave is currently problematic (particularly if one has family/commitments outside Ireland). In this regard, differences in levels of support between professional and support staff & academic staff were mentioned) – therefore this needs to be further explored. - Gender balance in leadership and decision-making: EDI training (in relation to awareness of using appropriate language at meetings etc.) to be delivered to all staff throughout TU Dublin, including senior and top management. - Gender equality in recruitment and career progression: Recruitment processes to be explored to increase inclusivity in the hiring process. - Data collection processes: Data collection to be increasingly intersectional and introduced at induction and when staff members update their staff cards.
<p>Main results of the second workshop</p>	<p>Three groups were formed. Four actions were co-designed. Topics discussed during the second workshop included: improving communication throughout the university (with an emphasis on respectful and sensitive language (for example, regarding gender and race); the need for awareness of EDI protocols to highlighted throughout the university; and the need for recruitment processes to become increasingly inclusive.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building a Community of Care - Improved understanding and awareness of EDI policy in TU Dublin including reporting mechanisms in place (will be implemented through 2 actions: TUD - Action 4 and TUD - Action 5) - Inclusive recruitment protocols and policies - Intersectional Awareness Trainings
<p>Results of the meeting with management</p>	<p>The meeting of the GEP working group with management took place on 24 April 2024 (online). There were 11 people altogether (two NEXUS team members facilitated the meeting). All attendees were female and included people from the university’s professional services: Assistant Head of Academic Affairs, Head of Decarbonisation, Sustainability Events and Senior Media Coordinator, Head of Human Resource Systems and Analytics, Head of Employee Engagement, Athena Swan Lead (Equality, Diversity and Inclusion directorate), Director of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion, Senior manager TrailblazHer (gender initiative),</p>

	<p>and Researcher Career Development Manager) as well as a senior lecturer.</p> <p>Three actions were presented ('EDI Champions', 'Enhanced EDI', and 'Inclusive recruitment protocols and policies'). Feedback and suggestions were provided from meeting participants. It was decided to proceed with the 'EDI Champions' action and the 'Enhanced EDI' (after the meeting it was decided the best way forward is to do develop an EDI Dashboard which will be implemented in collaboration the university EDI directorate actions). The 'EDI Champions' action will also be implemented in collaboration with the university EDI directorate.</p>
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3.1.2 Frederick University (FredU)

Open Labs dates	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
		4 April 2024		8 April 2024
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	10		11	
	Women: 7	Men: 3	Women: 8	Men: 3
	Internal: 10	External: 0	Internal: 10	External: 1
Scenario adopted	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders participating	Academics, Directors of Services, Top Management, Gender Equality Officer, President and Vice President of the Student's Union.			
Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating	CSOs (Director of The School for Deaf Children).			

<p>Main results of the first workshop</p>	<p>All participants were very interested to hear about the NEXUS Project and how it can contribute to improving university policies. The inequalities based on T2.2 results were presented. Two groups of five were formed.</p> <p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At national level, gender discrimination remains the most important area of inequality, as many topics are not resolved yet. Apart from gender, the next most important area concerns the persons with special needs, such as people/students with mobility difficulties, with hearing or sight deficiencies, and/or learning difficulties. - The inequality grounds mainly discussed were the students' disabilities. It was at this point that it was decided to invite stakeholders that come from relevant areas such as the School of the deaf or the School of the blind. <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture: Not an easy task, there were some suggestions such as to create a room for the extraction of milk and storage, give one day per week for work from home for the administrative staff, change the remuneration procedure during maternity leave. - Leadership and decision-making: Maintain the current policies and keep empowerment and motivating women to participate in the bodies of the university. - Recruitment and career progression: Create a document that monitors all decisions and includes also all policies regarding recruitment and progression. - Research and teaching content: To adopt the e-course from AGH University. - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: To continue the campaigns and make them more inclusive. - Data collection processes: As to change the Information System is not an easy task, it was discussed to implement the GEAM Tool more regularly to create a database to track the improvements.
<p>Main results of the second workshop</p>	<p>External stakeholders shared the needs of students with hearing deficiencies and how the university could facilitate these students to overcome the problems they face during their studies. Two actions were co-designed.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educate teaching and administrative staff to interact efficiently with students with hearing deficiency (FredU - Action 5) - Monitor GE in University through data collection (FredU - Action 2, AGH - Action 2, BZN - Action 2)
<p>Results of the meeting with management</p>	<p>Top Management were present in both Open Labs and they participated in the discussions and in the proposed actions, thus they are aware of the co-designed actions. The NEXUS Cyprus team will present the actions that were discussed and decided upon during the second Open Lab workshop to the management with the aim to get them approved. The management will be kept constantly informed during the implementation phase.</p>

3.1.3 Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski (UNISOFIA)

	Workshop 1	Workshop 2
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Open Labs dates	26 March 2024		2 April 2024	
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	14		15	
	Women: 11	Men: 3	Women: 12	Men: 3
	Internal: 9	External: 5	Internal: 10	External: 5
Scenario adopted	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders participating	Dean of Faculty, Human resources department, Vice Rectors of UNISOFIA, PhD Department, Main Rector's Secretary, Researcher Associate Professor, Researcher Professor, Statistical Analysis Department.			
Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating	Public bodies/decision makers (NCPQPS), Feminist organisations (Foundation for Woman and Center of Woman's Studies and Policies), RPOs/RFOs (Departments of National Ministry Science and Education of Bulgaria).			
Main results of the first workshop	<p>SU does not collect data on inequalities within the institution itself; however, it would be reasonable to collect, analyse and summarise them in the name of equality.</p> <p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marital status; beliefs; gender identity; socioeconomic status; disability; political views; educational qualifications; national and ethnic origin; refugee status. - Other aspects were discussed, including rules and policies that may be discriminatory, structural discrimination, workplace harassment and bullying, work-life balance, and ways of accessing support. <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture: Provide support to employees with children. - Leadership and decision-making: Create an increasingly inclusive environment. - Recruitment and career progression: Enhance the mentorship programmes that are available in the university. - Research and teaching content: Include gender sensitive matters in research, where possible. - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: Improve existing system in several directions. - Data collection processes: Gather and analyse more inclusive data. 			
Topics discussed in the second workshop	<p>Three actions were co-designed.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating a study room for children of the university's employees - Collection of data for the scientists and employees of the university (UNISOFIA - Action 4) - Expansion of the University's Center for Psychological Counselling and Research 			

	(UNISOFIA - Action 5)
Results of the meeting with management	<p>After the meeting with management it was decided that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There should be an increased focus on implementing consistent and targeted policies by management; - A positive culture and climate to support good work performance should be created; - Actions against violence (GBV) need more attention. It is necessary to increase awareness of GBV amongst all individuals in SU who work on the subject, through the implementation of various initiatives (with the participation of specialists), for example via/meetings, seminars, trainings, etc.; - There should also be a focus on mental health support and work-life balance measures. - The actions will be approved in the Academic Council vote.

3.1.4 Les Mans University (UM)

	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
Open Labs dates	16 May 2024		21 May 2024	
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	14		4	
	Women: 11	Men: 3	Women: 4	Men: 0
	Internal: 14	External: 0	Internal: 4	External: 0
Scenario adopted	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders participating	Researchers, teachers and administrative staff.			
Main results of the first workshop	<p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u> The groups discussed the specific inequality grounds. The key topics from the discussion included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusion: accessibility, adaptation, equality of opportunity, end of bias, mixed courses, more inclusive meetings (for example, meetings scheduled in an inclusive manner so as to allow for care obligations etc.), negotiation training for women. - Intersectionality: the need for recognising how inequality grounds intersect. - Discrimination: what discrimination means was discussed specifically, discrimination differentiates between individuals because of their particularity. While negative discriminations were deliberated upon, positive discrimination was also discussed. - Equality: Equality and equity were both discussed with it being noted that sometimes equality can be bad for women if understood in terms of “parity” because in order to 			

	<p>respect parity they will over solicit them.</p> <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture: Do not hold meetings during lunch breaks or too late in the evening so that everyone can be included. - Leadership and decision-making: A gender budget (because women ask less for grants than men for their research and projects). - Recruitment and career progression: Encourage women to negotiate their salaries during job meetings. - Research and teaching content: More gender-balanced courses and more female teachers in male dominated disciplines. - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: Increase resources for teachers and administrative staff to support people (students and coworkers) to understand and deal with (if it happens to them or if it is witnessed) sexual harassment.
Main results of the second workshop	<p>Two actions were co-designed.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To foster empowerment for women at work (UM - Action 4) - Gender, health, wellbeing, inclusive action for staff members and students (UM - Action 5)
Results of the meeting with management	<p>The GEP working group met the management (executive office and action plan monitoring committee) after the two workshops. All the actions designed were validated and they will be part of the next GEP of the university of Le Mans. The budget still needs to be discussed in June/July 2024, particularly regarding for the training courses that are part the first action. Discussions will take place with the departments concerned to ensure concrete implementation of the actions.</p>

3.1.5 AGH University of Kraków (AGH)

	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
Open Labs dates	10 April 2024		10 April 2024	
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	12		12	
	Women: 8	Men: 4	Women: 8	Men: 4
	Internal: 7	External: 5	Internal: 7	External: 5
Scenario adopted	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders participating	Researchers, HR and HR Excellence, Ombudsperson for Students Rights, Ombudsperson for Equality, Head of Research Projects Department, Students.			

Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating	National Science Centre NCN, National Centre for Academic Exchange NAWA, Municipality of Kraków, Kraków University of Arts, Polish Academy of Science.
Main results of the first workshop	<p>Katarzyna Leszczynska (responsible for the GEP at AGH) presented the context for the creation of the GEP, pointing out the institutional and research conditions that shaped the AGH GEP. This was followed by representatives of the NEXUS project presenting their report relating to the research findings: pointing out the problems and challenges that have arisen in the AGH GEP, but also the issues that (especially in the context of intersectionality) need to be deepened and operationalised.</p> <p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender remains a major area of discrimination; - Non-heteronormative and transgender people (especially students); - At the institutional level, the presence and recognition of migrants from Ukraine as an important part of the academic community among those studying and working at universities was discussed, particularly how their visibility (especially in the context of the war in Ukraine) has allowed for the introduction of some inclusion mechanisms; - Regarding the challenges of intersectionality, the need to reconcile two perspectives, such as the institutional perspective and the individual perspective, were noted. Also, relating to the complex situation of individuals associated with academia, the most relevant areas were considered to be gender-age quandaries, issues of family circumstances and career paths – particularly in relation to work-life balance. <p><u>Key objectives identified</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture: Self-help, bottom-up solutions. - Leadership and decision-making: Working at the Deans level. - Recruitment and career progression: Open and equal recruitment procedures. - Research and teaching content: trainings and online F2F scheme. - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: Necessity of development and implementation of a dictionary easily defining all manifestations of discrimination in organisation. - Data collection processes: Working on more intersectional data - necessity to check the law and regulations according to the data needed.
Main results of the second workshop	<p>Three groups were formed, and three actions were co-designed.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PIKOPIKA (Information policy) (AGH - Action 4) - Supervisory meetings - Organisational culture - wellbeing
Results of the meeting with management	<p>The NEXUS team has permission from the Rector of AGH University of Science and Technology to proceed with the actions.</p>

3.1.6 Bay Zoltán (BZN)

Open Labs dates	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
	25 April 2024		29 April 2024	
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	12		12	
	Women:	Men:	Women: 12	Men: 0
	Internal: 12	External: 0	Internal: 8	External: 4
Scenario adopted	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders participating	Middle management, Human resources department, researcher, project managers (support staff), project assistants (support staff).			
Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating	RPOs/RFOs (Hungarian Agricultural University, University of Pécs, Moholy-Nagy University).			
Main results of the first workshop	<p>Two groups were formed. Overall, the group discussions illustrate the need for a forum in the institution where internal organisational issues can be discussed (including inequalities and proposals for overcoming them).</p> <p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gender: less represented gender (e.g. males among biologists and project managers; females among engineers); - Age: age-related issues such as those encountered by for example, early career researchers and individuals nearing retirement or already retired; - Socioeconomic status: including regional, geographical and sectoral differences in pay defined by the job market. BZN, as a non-profit company, has to consider the demands and realities of the job market; - Disability/illness): specifically, health issues that may impact an individuals ability to work (for example, a certified medical condition that makes the bearer less than 100% fit for work). <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture: Eliminating prejudices, improving corporate culture. Sensitisation training - development of compassion and empathy. Creating an accurate picture of blind spots and the perception of equal opportunities. For this, designing a questionnaire, collecting data, planning new actions based on the answers, or updating existing ones was discussed. - Leadership and decision-making: Supporting individual professional development in fields in line with professional activity areas of the institute - e.g. (online training). Sensitisation of managers, recurring training of middle managers and team leaders in 			

	<p>helping and supporting colleagues. Progress towards balance of the underrepresented gender in leadership and senior research roles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruitment and career progression: Eliminating salary differences for early stage researchers in different professional fields. More effective integration of disadvantaged women in active work with innovative solutions. - Research and teaching content: More effective involvement of women in leading roles in tenders. Monitoring of effectiveness (The participation of female researchers in competitive proposals/tenders as leaders is low. We do not follow up the success rate by gender). - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: The survey mentioned under organisational culture may also cover this area. - Data collection processes: Data collection, data analysis, examination of trends, use of data to reduce inequalities in work related trainings (the participation rates along inequality dimensions can be measured, but we have not measured it so far).
Main results of the second workshop	<p>Three balanced groups were formed. Six actions were co-designed.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for leadership training - Eliminating gender discrimination in wages among junior researchers - Better measurement and follow-up of the participation rates in work-related training (BZN - Action 4, AGH - Action 3, FredU - Action 3) - Employing disadvantaged staff - Eliminating prejudices, improving corporate culture - everyone is important! (Error! Reference source not found.) - Team building event series.
Results of the meeting with management	<p>The working group met on 6 May 2024 to discuss the proposed actions put forward by the Open Labs and the twinning trio. The approval of the management as the ultimate internal decision-making body will be sought after the finalisation of the actions (in July 2024), upon the update of the institutional GEP document (which will also include the final actions).</p>

3.1.7 Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Niš (UN)

Open Labs dates	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
		15 March 2024		29 March 2024
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	19		18	
	Women: 10	Men: 9	Women: 11	Men: 7
	Internal: 12	External: 7	Internal: 11	External: 7
Scenario adopted	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders	Dean, Vice Dean, Human resources department, Council Head (Commissioner for gender equality), Trainers.			

<p>participating</p>	
<p>Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating</p>	<p>Companies (Johnson Electric, MENA Group), CSOs (Committee for Human Rights), RPOs/RFOs (Faculty of Law, Faculty of Occupational Safety).</p>
<p>Main results of the first workshop</p>	<p>Three groups were established, each with a moderator from the project team.</p> <p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u> Three minority groups in general were identified at the institutional level: ethnic minority (Roma), disabled individuals, and female students and employees. Three related inequality grounds were considered: GBV, disabled staff and students, Roma students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The most contentious issue in the discussion about GBV and sexual harassment was the presence of policies that exist only on paper and the evident lack of implementation. - Disability: It was concluded that there is not enough information and visibility regarding the problems people with disabilities encounter. Also, it was identified that there are limited opportunities for people using wheelchairs to actively engage in learning processes at the institution - due to issues of physical access to all necessary rooms. Also, the challenges faced by people with impaired vision were discussed particularly in relation to not being able to follow learning materials (lack of access to appropriate learning materials). - In the group discussing ethnicity, it was noted that there is a small number of Roma students, and that they have longer periods of study. <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discrimination: Improve visibility and conditions for disabled staff and students; improve admission and success rate of ethnic minority (Roma) students. - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: Improvements to current policies for preventing sexual and workplace harassment include raising awareness of the issue, informing the reporting of cases, and providing data on successful resolutions.
<p>Main results of the second workshop</p>	<p>Three groups were formed, and three actions were co-designed.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform employees and students about the existence of the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment at MFN (UN - Action 4) - Improved visibility of the faculty of Mechanical Engineering Nis as a good environment for persons with disability - Increase the number of Roma students at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering Nis (UN - Action 5)
<p>Results of the meeting with management</p>	<p>The meeting of the GEP working group with management took place on the 13th of May. After the presentation of the content and results of the two workshops, the discussion continued in a cooperative spirit about what can be realistically carried out in the coming period. It was emphasised that the NEXUS team should prepare an Activity Plan for a short</p>

	<p>period (one year, for the duration of the project) as well as an Activity Plan for a longer period, which will be included in the Faculty's Action Plan.</p> <p>The GEP working group has validated one of the designed actions from each open lab working group. The criteria for decision making were provided by the dean's office, including realistic expectations for financial resources necessary for the implementation of the proposed actions and the envisaged timeframe, which should correlate with the end of the NEXUS project. The GEP working group did not issue a request for formal approval of the Actions to the attention of the Faculty Management. Due to internal processes and regulations being part of an EU funded Work Plan, no further requirement would be needed to secure the implementation.</p>
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3.1.8 Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia (IIT)

Open Labs dates	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
		18 March 2024		8 April 2024
Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops	14		11	
	Women: 11	Men: 3	Women: 9	Men: 2
	Internal: 11	External: 3	Internal: 8	External: 3
Scenario adopted	Scenario 1 - Meeting with management in between the two workshops			
Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders participating	Research Organisation Directorate, Human Resources Directorate, Technology Transfer Directorate, the Research Unit, the Legal Office and the Communication Directorate. One researcher also attended.			
Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating	RPOs/RFOs (specifically, Fondazione Bruno Kessler and Fondazione Telethon).			
Main results of the first workshop	<p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disability: in line with national rules, IIT has data relating to “protected categories” that are collected before hiring. However, the inequality grounds that are not declared under the law are not currently mapped by IIT. - Socio-economic background/status: specifically, how it is defined, in terms of organisational role and corresponding salary. - Parenting: participants asked if and how data concerning parenthood is detected; they focused on services that might support parents, including nursery services. Difficulties in providing services requiring infrastructural availabilities were acknowledged. - Gender and gender identity: the difference between gender and gender identity and 			

	<p>what is meant by the term “gender” and by the term “identity” were identified as important.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethnicity and nationality: what is meant by the word “ethnicity” and how it differs from the topic of nationality. - Difficulty of data collection, i.e. how IIT should go about getting an employee/collaborator to share personal data with the organisation and for what purpose. <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: To foster an organisational culture interested in the harassment topic. - Data collection processes: To find ways to integrate data collection in the internal ERP systems.
<p>Main results of the second workshop</p>	<p>Facilitators shared the results from the first Open Lab and introduced the logic model. Participants were then divided into two groups—one focusing on workplace harassment and the other on data collection—based on their expertise and roles.</p> <p><u>Actions co-designed:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to handle harassment in the workplace (IIT - Action 1) - Designing ways to collect non-binary data (IIT - Action 2)
<p>Results of the meeting with management</p>	<p>The key objectives and the identified actions in the framework of the NEXUS project are a more inclusive way to develop actions in the existing Gender Equality Plan, already approved by the IIT management. The GEP WG had a meeting with the Human Capital and Organisation Director to update him about the actions designed in the Open Labs and in the Trios. The Director approved the actions proposed. As the actions co-designed comply with the IIT Gender Equality Plan that has already been approved by IIT Top Management, the Human Capital and Organisation Director approved the proposed actions in a meeting, an additional formal approval was considered unnecessary.</p>

3.1.9 Koç University (KU)

	Workshop 1		Workshop 2	
<p>Open Labs dates</p>	28 March 2024		29 March 2024	
<p>Participants in the two Open Lab Workshops</p>	10		11	
	Women: 9	Men: 1	Women: 11	Men: 0
	Internal: 6	External: 4	Internal: 7	External: 4
<p>Scenario adopted</p>	Scenario 2 - Meeting with management after the two workshops			
<p>Units/roles represented by internal stakeholders</p>	College of Science, KUSIF-Social Impact Forum, Alumni Office, Executive Education Programs, Sociology students.			

<p>participating</p>	
<p>Organisations represented by external stakeholders participating</p>	<p>Companies (Inan Network, Koç Holding), CSOs (Soroptimist), feminist organisations (SEBUKA).</p>
<p>Main results of the first workshop</p>	<p>Details of T2.2 were presented. Participants were interested in all the sections. They contributed to the presentation when they wanted to add something about inequalities. There were two groups.</p> <p><u>Inequality grounds identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socio-economic background: at the national level, socio-economic background was considered as the most important inequality ground. It was agreed that socio-economic background is an important area to focus in relation to focusing on new actions. From the discussion, the most controversial issue was the exclusion of blue-collar workers. - LGBTQI+: was discussed as important at the institutional level. - Intersectionality of religion and gender, and the intersectionality of seniority level and gender, were also discussed. <p><u>Key objectives identified:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture: Integrate increasingly inclusive care packages into the system. For example, single benefits, self-care benefits, aged care benefits, pet benefits, or flexible benefits may be included to minimise discrimination by socioeconomic background. - Recruitment and career progression: Although young researchers work hard, they cannot move up a grade. To tackle this problem, social mobility can be improved. - Research and teaching content: Due to economic conditions, PhD students living in crowded dormitories do not have an adequate environment for research. To eliminate inequalities based on socio-economic background at the doctoral level, PhD students' living conditions must be improved. - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment: Gender equality issues can be integrated into KOLT, ETPR, and UNIV 101.
<p>Topics discussed in the second workshop</p>	<p>Participants were enthusiastic about expressing their ideas regarding developing the outcomes of the first workshop. Four actions were co-designed.</p> <p>Actions co-designed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Skill Development Program (KU - Action 4) - Social Media Literacy Training (KU - Action 5) - Establishing a Care Network to fight imposter syndrome - Inclusive and diverse care packages
<p>Results of the meeting with management</p>	<p>Action 1 and Action 2 have been validated by the GEP working group. The actions were approved by the management of the institution: the person leading and coordinating GEP activities at KU was in constant close contact with decision making mechanisms and</p>

	leadership about the NEXUS activities. Full support and authority to proceed were granted in the process.
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3.2 Twin trio study visits

As mentioned above, the first set of study visits among the twin trios took place between the 15 April and 4 June. Two of the trios opted for a full in-person study visit at one of the partner institutions; one trio opted for a combination of online calls and an in-person study visit (FredU, AGH and BZN) in order to meet the set project deadlines.

In total, 10 actions were co-designed in the context of the twin trio study visits. All three twin trios opted for the harmonised approach, meaning that the actions will be implemented by all members of the respective trios, with institution-level adaptations.

The next section provides the reports of the study visits of the three trios. For details about the actions co-designed within the trios please consult Section 4.

3.2.1 Trio 1 – FredU, AGH, BZN

Location and date	Online; 12, 14 and 24 April. In person: Kraków, 4 June 2024.
Participants	<p>FredU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Petroula Mavrikiou, Associate Professor, Director of Gender Equality and Inclusion Research Unit - Antria Karaoli, Research Associate <p>AGH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Katarzyna Leszczyńska, Researcher and Head of Unit - Agnieszka Chrzęszcz, Head of Centre of e-Learning and Innovative Education - Kinga Sekerdej, Researcher - Edyta Tobiasiewicz, Researcher - Katarzyna Davassi, HR Unit - Jacek Gądecki, Vice Dean, Researcher <p>BZN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ádám Molnár, Head of Area, Knowledge Management Centre - Katalin Kurucz, Head of International Department (online meetings) <p>External stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ewa Stoeker, Coordinator for equality and diversity, Jagiellonian University <p>Gender breakdown: 7 women, 3 men</p>
Good practices on GE and inclusion (host organisation)	The Ombudsperson for Students Affairs and Ombudsperson for Equal Treatment presented the specific actions taken within their posts. Procedures and internal practices were described, in comparison to partners' practices as well. Special focus was given to intersectionality in their work, especially in terms of ethnicity (international students) and age (students vs teachers, employees) and status (administration and professors). In addition, the involvement of both Ombudsperson in the Academic Association of Safety and Equality (Akademicka sieć Bezpieczeństwa i Równości) was discussed, with a focus on prospects for collaboration.

Good practices on GE and inclusion (external stakeholders)	<p>Ewa Stoeker, coordinator for equality and diversity of the Jagiellonian University presented challenges that are related to intersectionality: lack of protection for the students in the current documents (Anti-discrimination Act), supporting transgender and non-binary students in the prolonged transition processes, cooperation with students centres and other academic units (e.g., providing psychological support and psychiatrist appointments free of charge).</p>
Good practices on GE and inclusion (guests)	<p>Frederick University</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code of conduct on sexual harassment - Campaigns on GBV - Girls in STEM Campaigns <p>BZN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance actions: work arrangements, special compensation available for employees in vulnerable situations
Actions co-designed in the Trio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality (FredU - Action 1, AGH - Action 1, BZN - Action 1) - Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool (GEAM) (FredU - Action 2, AGH - Action 2, BZN - Action 2) - Fostering participation in work-related trainings through data collection with a gender+ perspective (FredU - Action 3, AGH - Action 3, BZN - Action 4) - Inclusive communication guidelines (FredU - Action 4, Error! Reference source not found., BZN - Action 3)
Next steps agreed	<p>By the second study visit in Nicosia in September 2024:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality: translation in English - Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool (GEAM): decide on which sections to be included in the questionnaire - Fostering participation in work-related trainings through data collection with a gender+ perspective: Gather data available - Inclusive communication guidelines: desk research

3.2.2 Trio 2 – TUD, KU, UNISOFIA

Location and date	Istanbul, 17 and 18 April 2024
Participants	<p>KU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Behice Pehlivan, Gender Equality Coordinator - Ayca Çavdar, Doctoral Researcher <p>UNISOFIA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valentina Mitkova, Associate Professor - Natalia Rekova, Researcher <p>TUD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Catherine Bolger, Sexual Violence Prevention and Response Manager - Caitriona Delaney, Research Officer <p>External stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bahar Taşkın Öztürk, Chief Growth Officer of Twiser / Founder of Inequality Awareness Network; Founding President of INAN Association, inequality awareness network
	Gender breakdown: 7 women
Good practices on GE and inclusion (host organisation)	<p>Presentation by Behice Pehlivan of a selection of good practices on GE & inclusion at KU. Namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Return-to Research Grant; - Gender Inclusive Teaching Improvement Grant; - Inaugural Report on International Women’s Day; - Interview Series on Women in Science (for 11 February); - Sustainability & Inclusivity Curriculum Poster Series; - International Staff Week in İstanbul (Gender Equality in Academia & Innovative Aspect); - EMBO Self-Leadership Workshop for Women in Science; - Zone Campaign for fostering awareness for an inclusive and safe campus;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative project with UCC on Creating an interdisciplinary network for gender mainstreaming in medical education. <p>This presentation also included a detailed account of the background story of design and development of the institutional Gender Equality Plan that was launched in 2022. This was followed by a fruitful discussion on common challenges for EDI practitioners in implementing gender equality actions in research and innovation institutions and creative strategies to overcome them.</p>
Good practices on GE and inclusion (external stakeholders)	<p>Presentation by Bahar Taşkın Öztürk of the Inequality Awareness Network (INAN) on good practices on GE and inclusion in the workplace. The INAN foundation aims to address challenges of gender equality in the workplace. Their perspective is that this must start with each of us and our capacity to spread this awareness. INAN focuses on Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion and they have collaborated with the Harvard Business Review. The presenter shared her commitment to societal impact and blending business acumen with meaningful change. She also discussed her much renowned podcast/YouTube series called 'Sesi Açıyoruz' (We turn up the sound) through which she aims to raise individual awareness on equality, diversity and inclusion, especially gender equality (her latest video was showcased as the special 8 March event of the Harvard Business Review (Türkiye's popular video streaming channel). She also talked about her experience during the NEXUS Open Lab that she participated in and about her plans to collaborate more with the Gender Equality Office at Koç University.</p>
Good practices on GE and inclusion (guests)	<p>TUD</p> <p>Presentation by Catherine Bolger, in which she shared various practices she is involved with in TU Dublin. These include the TU Dublin Ending Sexual Violence Implementation Plan 2022-2024; the Speak Out Tool, Workshops for students: consent workshops to all first years during orientation; bystander intervention workshops; and disclosure training for sports captains, society leads, student leaders and ambassadors; Workshops for staff: online consent awareness video screening; bystander intervention training; disclosure training for all staff; training for Investigators and panels.</p> <p>Presentation by Caitriona Delaney on other good practices at TUD namely: Race Equity Action Plan (2021-2023); Race Equity Community of Practice; Community Development and Youth Work Programme. The main highlights of the discussion were: Sharing challenges encountered when trying to implement good practices and the ways to circumvent these barriers so as to increase institutional inclusion.</p> <p>UNISOFIA</p> <p>Presentation by Valentina Mitkova of the following good practices that are in place in Sofia University: 1) The Quota Principle for accepting male/female student applicants which is part of the institutional policy of Sofia University; 2) National scholarship "For Women in Science" in Bulgaria: launched in 2010 by the National Commission for UNESCO - Bulgaria, Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" and L'Oréal Bulgaria; 3) MATILDA: the joint European Master Degree in Women's and Gender History linking six leading European universities; 4) Aspasia. The International Yearbook of Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern European Women's and Gender History published by Berghahn Books (with researchers from Sofia University as contributors and as members of the editorial team).</p>
Actions co-designed in the Trio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GBV Training and Awareness Online Module (TUD - Action 1, KU - Action 1, UNISOFIA - Action 1) - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis (TUD - Action 2, KU - Action 2, UNISOFIA - Action 2) - Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success (TUD - Action 3, KU - Action 3, UNISOFIA - Action 3)
Next steps agreed	<p>Ongoing monthly online meetings to be continued and, if necessary, these meetings will be held more frequently. For example, a meeting was held on 30 April (after a few days of</p>

	<p>the Study Visit) to select and refine the co-designed actions to be implemented in the trio (after the study visit there were five actions to choose from and three actions were chosen to advance as a trio).</p> <p>The next trio study visit will take place in December 2024 in Dublin on the 15th and 16th of October 2024.</p>
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3.2.3 Trio 3 – IIT, UM, UN

Location and date	Genova, 15 and 16 April 2024
Participants	<p>IIT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lina Donnarumma, Diversity and Inclusion Manager - Vanessa DeLuca, Diversity and Inclusion Specialist - Martina Cicaloni, Diversity and Inclusion Fellow - Gloria Okojie, Diversity and Inclusion Support Assistant <p>Les Mans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Angelina Etiemble, Maîtresse de Conférences <p>UN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marko Mančić, Assistant Professor <p>Gender breakdown: 6 women, 1 man</p>
Good practices on GE and inclusion (host organisation)	<p>The Diversity and Inclusion Office was created in 2021 as part of the human resources directorate.</p> <p>The team organised two training sessions on intersectionality and intersectoriality in March, and two Open Labs between March and April. It was attended by IIT staff such as researchers and administrative staff from the Unit HR & Technology Transfer & Research</p>

	<p>directorate. They presented the NEXUS project with its goals and partners. The logical model and methodology used to develop what emerged from the Open Labs were explained at length. About 32 people from different departments participated in about six hours of workshops. Three expert partners working in science and STEAM were also invited but only two later attended and contributed to the two meetings.</p> <p>As a result of the work, it was then possible to identify two work activities for the coming months through the NEXUS project, the first related to a training activity on the topic of harassment and GBV in the workplace, and the second on the collection of data on non-binary people.</p>
<p>Good practices on GE and inclusion (external stakeholders)</p>	<p>UN Presentation by Marko Mančić representing the University of Nis on activities undertaken so far in the context of NEXUS (Open Labs).</p> <p>UM Presentation of a monitoring committee at UM for the current professional equality plan to carry out the assessment of the first plan and build the new GEP in 2024. The committee is made up of the university's management team, the human resources and central services departments, as well as the occupational psychologist, the occupational health and safety manager and the communications department. Staff representatives (trade union) participate in the monitoring committee.</p> <p>The aim is to introduce more intersectionality and inclusion (disability, minorities, migrants, etc.) into the next GEP. The French Ministry has given them 200 KPIs to achieve (42 so far) on subjects such as: the gender pay gap, the distribution between types of leave, taking on responsibility. The results will be used to gain a better understanding of the gender pay gap and take steps to reduce it.</p> <p>To implement the GEP, they have decided to create a call for volunteers to become "equality advisors" (10 to 15 people). The purpose is to facilitate the dissemination of actions in favour of equality, and to identify the specific needs of the university's various faculties.</p>
<p>Good practices on GE and inclusion (guests)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Influence of biases in decision-making (IIT - Action 3, UM - Action 1, UN - Action 1) - Gender+ dimension in research (IIT - Action 4, UM - Action 2, UN - Action 2) - Parenting Resource Group (Error! Reference source not found., UM - Action 3, UN - Action 3)
<p>Actions co-designed in the Trio</p>	<p>It was found out that partners work in very different organisational contexts where the topic of gender differences, GBV, and intersectionality is known differently.</p> <p>While IIT has had the GEP and a dedicated working unit for years, the University of Nis still has no such documents or recommendations. They planned two workshops before the Open Labs as a kick-off activity about the topic, and to create a positive environment in which to grow these issues.</p>
<p>Next steps agreed</p>	<p>During the study visit, the agenda of the periodic meetings was planned – possible dates for the next trio visit were also identified, the next one will be in France hosted by the University of Les Mans in October 2024, and the last one in Serbia in 2025.</p>

4 Pilot actions overview and booklet

This section presents the pilot actions co-designed and selected by the implementing partners within the Open Labs and the twin trios. Out of 45 pilot actions, twenty-four actions (53%) resulted from the co-creation in the twin trios; 15 actions (33%) resulted from co-creation in the Open Labs; six actions (13%) resulted from both the Open Labs and the twin trios (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Share of actions to be implemented by type of co-design.

Each action belongs to one or more thematic areas. In terms of the main thematic area of each action (see Figure 8), 14 actions (31%) focus on gender equality in recruitment and career progression; 12 actions (27%) focus on work-life balance and organisational culture; eight actions (18%) focus on measures against GBV including sexual harassment; six actions (13%) focus on the integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content; five actions (11%) have a primary focus on data collection. None of the actions have a main focus on gender balance in leadership and decision-making.

Overall, 14 actions (31%) involve data collection (as a main or secondary focus). In addition, 24 actions (53%) have an intersectoral component (see Figure 9). The types of external stakeholders that will be involved are shown in Figure 10, although some still have to be defined.

- Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
- Work-life balance and organisational culture
- Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
- Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
- Data collection

Figure 8: Share of actions by primary thematic area addressed.

- Intersectoral
- Not intersectoral

Figure 9: Share of actions with an intersectoral component.

Figure 10: Number of actions to be implemented per type of external stakeholder involved.

Considering the intersectional dimensions beyond sex and gender (see Figure 11), disability is included in 33 actions, followed by gender identity (31 actions), age (31 actions), ethnicity/race (27 actions) and sexual orientation (21 actions). Other intersectional dimensions addressed include nationality, family/parental status, socioeconomic status and religion/belief, as well as neurodiversity, mental health, job title/seniority and educational level. A disclaimer is needed as far as gender identity is concerned, as retrospectively this dimension might have been subject to misinterpretation in the reporting process: while the templates were formulated taking for granted that all actions would deal with gender as a dimension, gender identity was meant to represent trans/queer identities as an additional intersectional component. Yet, the high rate of actions leads to suspect that this could have been misunderstood by partners as gender as such. Further checks will be made and the final accurate result included in D3.2, *Formative evaluation mid-term results*.

Figure 11: Number of actions to be implemented per intersectional dimension beyond sex and gender.

The actions below are organised by implementing partner.

4.1 Technological University Dublin

TUD - Action 1	
Action title	GBV Training and Awareness Online Module
Key objective	Develop a skill and knowledge-based online module to educate and raise awareness on GBV and provide strategies that will both deal with and combat GBV in the partner institutions and beyond.
Thematic area	Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Sex and gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, nationality, race & ethnicity, age (inclusiveness beyond gender will be institute specific).
Intersectoral component	Yes, a consultation meeting with NGOs working towards ending GBV will be conducted before the module is finalised.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design time; - Collating the module materials; - The module platform will need to be organised.

Audience	Staff and students throughout partner institutions and beyond.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create module content; - Consultation with NGOs working in the field; - Create platform to host module; - Develop networks to disseminate the module through; - Launch module: Launch event (webinar) on 8 March to showcase the module (this will also raise the visibility and reach of NEXUS).
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024: The GBVM (GBV module) project plan will be developed in detail with concrete items (action items, strict deadlines, target audience, module structure, tech requirements, overhead, budgetary requirements, etc.); - June - July 2024: All foundational instructional and training materials will be compiled; - August - September 2024: Online module instructional content is worked on and finalised after consultation with NGOs. Simultaneously, the technicalities of the platform will be being outlined and resolved; - September - October 2024: Visual design of the module content with Zone campaign elements will be made by the Circle Design Group at KU in collaboration with UniSofia tech team; - Release module on 8 March 2025.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30 people per partner institution will have completed the module by February 2025; - The quality of the module will be measured by a post-module evaluation completed by individuals who have taken the course.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals in the partner institutions and beyond will have access to the online module; - Increased awareness and understanding of GBV; - Increased visibility of the NEXUS project.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The module will include an assessment of an individual's understanding and awareness of GBV; - The online module about GBV will improve awareness and understanding of what GBV is; - The GBV online module will provide strategies and information about how to deal with experiences of GBV (both observed & experienced personally); - This online module will be a resource for those working in the partner institutions (and beyond) to improve their GBV related practice.

TUD - Action 2	
Action title	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis
Key objective	To ascertain the baseline needs in relation to mentoring in the partner institutions and to subsequently develop a mentoring programme.

Thematic area	Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Progression
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender (including gender identity); disability; race & ethnicity; nationality; age; family status.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Data is being collected as part of this action – the data collection will include questions/survey items designed to collect intersectional data.
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Person/persons to construct the survey to be compiled; - Teams from each university to administer the survey; - Teams from each university to analyse the survey data; - Person/persons to compile a report on the findings of the survey.
Audience	Potential mentors and potential mentees.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Construct survey; - Administer survey; - Analyse results; - Disseminate results via each institution's website.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By 30 July 2024: Complete Survey Draft will be ready; - July - August 2024: Feedback and suggestions will be collected from institutional stakeholders to improve the survey; - By 30 August 2024: Survey structure will be ready and final; - September 2024: Online survey platform will be built; - September 2024: Necessary institutional approval to run the survey will be collected (e.g., ethical board approvals); - 1 October 2024 – 1 November 2024: Administer the survey; - 15 November 2024 - 15 December 2024: Survey analysis; - 11 February 2025: Social media dissemination of the survey results in infographic format to raise awareness of the findings.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Completed surveys (60 people minimum per institution to complete the survey); - Report on survey findings.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship will be conducted; - A mentoring training programme (manual) will be developed; - Results of the survey will be published on the NEXUS website and disseminated via social media on 11 February 2025 the Day of Women and Girls in Science.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each institution will have increased understanding of what skills mentors need to be effective mentors; - Each institution will have increased understanding of what mentees need to advance their careers in a holistic, supportive and quality manner; - This action will provide critical insights regarding the career advancement needs of early career researchers who experience intersectional inequalities, thus illustrating the challenges faced by such individuals.

TUD - Action 3	
Action title	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success
Key objective	To develop a training programme/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action “Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis”.
Thematic area	Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Progression
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender (including gender identity); disability; race & ethnicity; nationality; age; family status.
Intersectoral component	Yes, the external stakeholders are yet to be identified. It is envisioned that some of the mentors will be from business/industry/CSOs. Specifically, professionals from industry will be approached and encouraged to be mentors, to strengthen the academy-industry link, potentially enhancing the career prospects of doctoral students and early career researchers who would like the opportunity to use their expertise and transversal skills in industry.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training materials; - Time from mentors and mentees.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mentors (experienced individuals in academia and research as well as in the industry, business and NGO/CSO worlds); - Mentees (Doctoral students & ECR); - DEI Officers & mentoring program administrators in HEI.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gather materials to use in the programme; - Put together the manual for the programme; - Target suitable individuals inside partner institutions to be mentors; - Target suitable individuals from the industry, business and NGO/CSO spheres to be mentors.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 13 January 2025 - 9 June 2025: Compile the mentoring programme manual; - July 2025: Launch mentoring programme.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training programmes for mentors and mentees will be developed.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Programme/training manuals for mentors will be produced.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A mentorship programme with inclusivity at its core will be established; - This programme will enhance university-industry relations and intersectorality of academia, thus increasing the total inter-connectivity of research and innovation ecosystems; - The career prospects of early career researchers (doctoral students, post docs, junior faculty) will be developed - regarding - self-confidence,

	transversal skills and transitions to industry.
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TUD - Action 4	
Action title	EDI Dashboard
Key objective	To increase awareness of EDI initiatives, resources and policy throughout the institution.
Thematic area	Work Life Balance & Organisational Culture
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Will include inclusive data available at the institution (disability, race & ethnicity)
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Materials to populate the dashboard; - Human resource to create the dashboard; - Human resource to monitor dashboard traffic; - Collaboration with the EDI office.
Audience	Staff and students throughout Dublin.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gather information in collaboration with the EDI office; - Create dashboard; - Launch dashboard; - Set up a system to monitor traffic to the dashboard.
Time-frame	Implementation to begin in June 2024.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dashboard will be accessible to all staff in TU Dublin; - Traffic on the dashboard will be monitored.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to navigate EDI dashboard; - EDI resources and information readily available.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Staff throughout TU Dublin will have increased awareness of the EDI initiatives, resources and policy throughout the institution; - Increased confidence in and understanding of disclosures.

TUD - Action 5	
Action title	EDI Champions
Key objective	To create an EDI champion network throughout TU Dublin thus embedding individuals who: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have an interest in, and commitment to, advancing equality, diversity and

	<p>inclusion within their department and, where appropriate, across the University;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are familiar with how to access or get advice on relevant policies, procedures and legislation; - Are a visible and proactive Champion of EDI within their department/unit.
Thematic area	Work Life Balance and Organisational Culture
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender, including gender identity; race & ethnicity; disability.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Materials to create handbook; - Room for the launch.
Audience	Staff members interested in and committed to advancing EDI throughout TU Dublin
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create EDI champion handbook; - Create EDI champion network; - Train EDI champion; - Create a template/way of supporting EDI champions.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024 Create EDI champion handbook; - September 2024 Train EDI champions; - November 2024 Launch EDI champion 'campaign'.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EDI champion handbook - 1 EDI champion per unit (school/department/service) to act as a key conduit between their department/service, the EDI office and the wider university on EDI issues.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EDI champion network; - Handbook for EDI champions to be created; - EDI Champions tasked with embedding EDI within their area of work by promoting and communicating equality, diversity and inclusivity information about key events, news, training opportunities, issues, policy developments and best practice will be in place throughout the university; - EDI champions will be in a position to contribute to broader cultural change and raising awareness of EDI issues by engaging with staff networks, the EDI office and other relevant EDI structures/groups; - Equality Champions will support the development of resources to highlight and share good EDI practice across the University.
Impact	A working and learning environment which is fair, welcoming and inclusive and where staff and students can fulfil their potential.

4.2 Frederick University

FredU - Action 1	
Action title	E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality
Key objective	Create an e-course with a Gender Equality and Intersectionality approach; Increase/Improve equality and diversity in research content.
Thematic area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.
Level of co-design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Twin trio: the Intersectional component and localisation/context specific element was designed with the trio; - The e-course will be translated and localised, which requires a context-specific approach as cultural and organisational context of the partners is different.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity.
Intersectoral component	Yes. Polish Research Agencies as evaluators for possible future implementation on the national/ regional level). An external stakeholder from a research centre (National Science Centre in Poland) will be involved in the testing and evaluation of the course.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polish version of the E-course; - Course content including infographics, charts, data, activities, quizzes and cases; - Work-load: translation localisation, redesign, implementation.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers; - Support staff; - PhD students; - Research agencies in Cyprus.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation of the files for translation; - Translating the documents and graphics into English. - Identify areas of the E-course that require context-specific module content; - Intersectionality: identify areas where various sectoral dimensions are not addressed sufficiently; - Redesigning and replacing the content according to localisation and intersectional analysis; - Launch the E-course on E-learning platforms; - Recruit users/ participants; - Evaluate E-course.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May – June 2024: Initial review for intersectional aspects by AGH; - July - August 2024: Translation into English by AGH; - September 2024: Release the course for the partners in English; - September 2024: Discussions on the intersectional dimension (combined with Cyprus SV);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - November 2024: Recommendations for changes in/to English course; - December 2024: Implement the recommendations in/from English version in the E-course; - January 2025: E-course ready for review from Frederick University top management; - January 2025: Recruitment of the participants.
Outputs	One English version of the course 2.0 (with intersectional changes).
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers will be better equipped to consider integrating gender, ethnicity, age etc into their research design and execution; - Researchers will be able to recruit more diverse and inclusive team members; - Support staff will be able to draw attention to imbalances and inform the researchers about opportunities brought by diversity practices in research design; - Increased awareness of inclusion and gender inequality in research.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased awareness of diversity and equality in designing and conducting research with a view to increasing intersectionality in research conducted at the Trio institutions; - Improved understanding of the importance and benefits of incorporating gender, age, ethnicity etc. dimensions in research; - Student and staff will have access to the E-course to improve awareness of intersectionality and research.

FredU - Action 2	
Action title	Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool
Key objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gather data from the GEAM Survey; - Map the situation regarding gender equality in FredU; - Create an updated database for each Institution; - Be able to make comparisons, keep track of changes, improvements or pitfalls.
Thematic area	Data collection processes in the following areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work life balance and organisational culture; - Gender equality and career progression; - Gender balance in leadership and decision making; - Measures against gender base violence, including sexual harassment.
Level of co-design	Both FredU Open Labs and twin trio. Each partner will decide which sections of the GEAM tool will be used and included in the survey. The Joint Action suggests that the GEAM Tool is implemented in the three institutions. For AGH and BZN is a new Action. For FredU it will be the second time to implement the tool. The tool is offered in English, Polish and Greek. Some sections of the questionnaire will not be used by all as the questionnaire addresses many areas. Its newest version includes questions addressed to the administrative staff and students.
Intersectional dimensions	Gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, other minority identities.

beyond gender	
Intersectoral component	Yes. The GEAM Tool is designed by external stakeholders.
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	A survey in English, Polish and/or Greek on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruitment and Promotion - Training - Work-life Balance - Parental leave - Organisational Culture and Climate: GE and Working Culture - Bullying, Harassment and Microaggressions
Audience	Faculty, staff and/or students.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact the owners of the questionnaire; create an admin account; - Activate the survey; - Contact the authorities of each institution to distribute the questionnaire; - Send the survey to faculty and/or staff and students; - Get the results.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024: Finalise the decision and contact the owners of the questionnaire to create the user accounts; - July - August 2024: Review and decide which questions to be included in the questionnaire; - September 2024: Discussions with the authorities of FredU; - October 2024: Launch of the survey; - November 2024: Wait for the survey responses; - December: Retrieve the results.
Outputs	Results on the current situation of GE in Frederick University.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to map and monitor the GE situation in Frederick University; - Ability to minimise gaps and inequalities.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase gender equality awareness; - Make gender inequalities visible; - Allow faculty and staff to express themselves anonymously; - Allow policy makers to make informed decisions.

FredU - Action 3	
Action title	Fostering participation in work-related trainings through data collection with a gender+ perspective
Key objective	Data collection and analysis to map the situation and establish the short-term trends of the participation of staff in professional training by gender and other inequality areas.
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

Level of co-design	Both BZN Open Labs and twin trio.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, job title (including managerial pos. for academics), type of training
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statistics (data) of training participation of different groups; - Identified data collection variables; data from the Services of the University.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All employees; - Underrepresented groups specified in the analysis.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop variables for collecting data; - Extract the data from the database, taking into account the last three full years; - Conduct data analysis; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data will be analysed for the years 2022-2023, 2023-2024, 2024-2025 (Data for 2022-2023 are already available). - Follow-up with actions to ensure more inclusivity (specific to the institution).
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rolled out over three academic years; - Annual statistical analysis, in correlation with the annual training plans of the institution.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Produce a report to include: analysis of inequalities/gaps of participation regarding the dimensions of inclusiveness.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the gender distribution of participation in training at FredU; - Preparing intervention (actions) based on the results of the data collection influencing forthcoming training plans of the institutions; - Training at FredU will attract and include a more inclusive audience.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring the distribution of participation in training at FredU and take informed decisions how to improve the rates; - Revealing discrimination instances and possible blind spots; - Making trainings more accessible to various employee groups, making the institution more inclusive

FredU - Action 4	
Action title	Inclusive communication guidelines
Key objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design guidelines to make communication within and outside the university fairer and more inclusive; - Enhance competences: knowledge, skills and attitudes; - Provide the community with a practical guidance on communication patterns in English for inclusive language;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set standards for internal and external communication; - Share lessons learned and support mutual learning among the Trio.
Thematic area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture - Gender balance in leadership and decision making - Gender equality in recruitment and career progression - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Twin trio. A section will be dedicated for guidelines in Polish for AGH; Inclusion of internal stakeholders (AGH: cooperation with students). FredU and BZN will have the document in English only.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, sexual orientation, ethnicity & race, age, religion & belief, disability, mental health & neurodiversity
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	Personal workload (time) of internal and external experts as well as of students to compile the guidelines on inclusive language, editing and writing.
Audience	FredU community and external stakeholders; University's community: employees and students; External stakeholders (e.g., other universities, research agencies, companies collaborating with the university, NGOs).
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students desk research (AGH); - Short interviews with staff and students (AGH); - Content development based on the above (shared task amongst the Trio group); - Final editing of the guidelines (shared task amongst the Trio group); - Publish the guidelines (shared task amongst the Trio group).
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May - June 2024: students desk research (AGH); - June - September 2024: short interviews with staff and students (AGH); - September 2024: discuss the progress and status in Cyprus during the second study visit; - October - November 2024: content development by sharing the work among the three institutions; - December 2024: review by the authorities at FredU and approval; - February 2025: Publish guidelines.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidelines to be used/available for use in the official communication of the university/research organization internally and externally, between academics/administrative staff but also with students; - A digital document with user-friendly layout.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workshop held for the Trio group to facilitate sharing good practices and transferring knowledge on inclusive communication; - Enhancement of the professional and personal communication: specifically regarding oral and written communication; - More inclusive work and study environment.
Impact	- FredU will have improved communication - internally and externally;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication will be fairer and more inclusive; - Enhanced communication competences; Enhanced communication standards.
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FredU - Action 5	
Action title	Annual training from an external speaker on GE and intersectionality under the Personal and Professional Committee (P2DF)
Key objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide annual training to staff and faculty on how to facilitate either disabled student, minorities, LGBTQI+, migrants etc.; - Increase awareness on the topic; - Inform the decisions of the policy makers of the university; - Inform the faculty of the university about their rights; - Improve the personal and professional development of the faculty; - Follow the trends on GE and intersectionality in other European Universities.
Thematic area	Work life balance and organisational culture
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Disability, sexual orientation, age. The topic will be intersectional.
Intersectoral component	Yes. External stakeholders will be invited to provide the training.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	Time and inputs from the Committee for personal and professional development-Personal and Professional Committee (P2DF).
Audience	Faculty and staff of FredU.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discussions with the Personal and Professional Committee (P2DF) on which external stakeholders or internal stakeholders to invite; - Include the training in the annual design of the Program; - Reach the stakeholders and invite them to provide the training; - Contact the potential trainer; - Decide on the topic; - Arrange the logistics (tickets accommodation if foreigner); - Inform P2DF Committee; - Set the dates; - Disseminate the event; - From 2024 FredU will include at least one training course on GE and intersectionality to address the following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Recruitment and Promotion; o Work-life Balance; o Disabilities and accessibility at the University (a training is foreseen on hearing deficiency). - Send an evaluation questionnaire.

Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024 : Suggest topics to P2DF Committee; - September 2024: Decide on the topic; - October 2024: Contact the potential trainer; - November 2025: Arrange the logistics (tickets accommodation if foreigner); - January 2025: Set the dates and disseminate the event; - March - April 2025: Training and evaluation questionnaire.
Outputs	Annual training: At least one training per year on GE and intersectionality.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of GE increased; - Staff and faculty empowered; - Staff and faculty Informed about new GE trends in Europe and globally.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved learning procedure for students; - Increased awareness on GE throughout FredU; - Gender inequalities made increasingly visible; - Knowledge transferred from abroad, - Successful practices embedded at FredU - FredU policy makers allowed to make informed decisions/in a position to make informed decisions; - Improved work life balance and organisational culture at the university.

4.3 Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski

UNISOFIA - Action 1	
Action title	GBV Training and Awareness Online Module
Key objective	Develop a skill and knowledge-based online module to educate and raise awareness on GBV and provide strategies to both deal with and to combat it in partner institutions and beyond.
Thematic area	Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Sex and gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, nationality, race & ethnicity, (inclusiveness beyond gender will be institute specific).
Intersectoral component	Yes
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design time; - Collating the module materials; - The module platform will need to be organised.
Audience	Staff and students throughout partner institutes and beyond
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create module content; - Create platform to host module; - Develop networks to disseminate the module through;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch module.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024: GBVM (GBV module) project plan will be developed in detail with concrete items (action items, strict deadlines, target audience, module structure, tech requirements, overhead, budgetary requirements, etc.); - June - July 2024: All foundational instructional and training materials will be compiled; - August - September 2024: Online module instructional content is worked on and finalised. Simultaneously, the technicalities of the platform are being outlined and resolved; - September - October 2024: Visual design of the module content with Zone campaign elements will be made by the Circle Design Group at KU in collaboration with UniSofia tech team; - Release module on 8 March 2025.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30 people per partner institution will have completed the module by February 2025; - The quality of the module will be measured by post module evaluation completed by individuals who have taken the course.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals in the partner institutions and beyond will have access to the online module; - Increased awareness and understanding of GBV; - Increased visibility of NEXUS project.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The module will include an assessment of individuals understanding and awareness of GBV; - Online module about GBV will improve awareness and understanding of what GBV; - Online module about GBV will provide strategies and information on how about to deal with experiences of GBV (observed & experienced personally); - An online module about GBV will be a resource for those working in the partner institutions (and beyond) to improve their practice.

UNISOFIA - Action 2	
Action title	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis
Key objective	To ascertain the base line needs in relation mentoring in the partner institutions and to subsequently develop a mentoring programme.
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender (including gender identity); disability; race & ethnicity; nationality; age; family status.

Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Yes. Baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship will be the result of a survey/ data collection among PhD students and young researchers at Sofia University.
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Person/persons to construct the survey to be compiled; - Teams from each university to administer the survey; - Teams from each university to analyse the survey data; - Person/persons to compile a report on the findings of the survey.
Audience	Potential mentors and potential mentees.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Construct survey; - Administer survey; - Analyse results; - Disseminate results via each institution's website.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By 30 July 2024: Complete survey draft ready; - July - August 2024: Feedback and suggestions will be collected from institutional stakeholders to improve the survey; - By 30 August 2024: Survey structure will be ready and final; - September 2024: Online survey platform will be built; - September 2024: Necessary institutional approval to run the survey will be collected (e.g., ethical board approvals); - 1 October 2024 - 1 November 2024: Administer the survey; - 15 November 2024 - 15 December 2024: Survey analysis; - 11 February 2025: Social media dissemination of the survey results in infographic format to raise awareness of the findings.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Completed surveys (60 people minimum per institution to complete the survey); - Report on survey findings.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship will be conducted; - A mentoring training programme (manual) will be developed.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each institution will have increased understanding of what skills mentors need to be effective mentors; - Each institution will have increased understanding of what mentees need to advance their careers in a holistic, supportive and quality manner.

UNISOFIA - Action 3	
Action title	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success
Key objective	To develop a training programme/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action "Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis"
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender (including gender identity); disability; race & ethnicity; nationality; age; family status.
Intersectoral component	Yes, the external stakeholders are yet to be identified. It is envisioned that some of the mentors will be from business/industry/CSOs.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training materials; - Time from mentors and mentees.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mentors (experienced individuals in academia and in the industry, business and NGO/CSO worlds); - Mentees (Doctoral students & ECR).
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gather materials to use in the programme; - Put together the manual for the programme; - Target suitable individuals inside partner institutions to be mentors; - Target suitable individuals from the industry, business and NGO/CSO spheres to be mentors.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 13 January 2025 – 9 June 2025: Compile the mentoring programme manual; - July 2025: Launch mentoring programme.
Outputs	Training programmes for mentors and mentees will be developed.
Outcomes	Programme/training manuals for mentors will be produced.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A mentorship programme with inclusivity at its core will be established; - This programme will enhance university-industry relations and intersectorality of academia, thus increasing the total inter-connectivity of research and innovation ecosystems; - The career prospects of early career researchers (doctoral students, post docs, junior faculty) will be developed - regarding - self-confidence, transversal skills and transitions to industry.

UNISOFIA - Action 4	
Action title	Collection of data for the scientists and employees of the university
Key objective	To strengthen the University's reputation as inclusive educational institution and workplace that wants to attract the most talented students and staff, regardless of their personal and social background; To create a tolerant culture where everyone is treated equally and where diversity is interpreted as a strength rather than a challenge.
Thematic area	Data collection processes
Level of co-design	Open Labs

Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age, socioeconomic status, disabilities.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	Participation of experts from different departments to carry out the monitoring, statistics and analysis (Department "Analysis and processing of data"; For example, experts from: Department "Human resources"; Department "Doctoral Students", the GEP working group, etc.)
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University students; - Academic staff; - Administrative staff.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data collection and percentage monitoring; - Analysis of the data collected; - Report the results (trends, developments, problematic issues within the institution).
Time-frame	Exact dates to be confirmed.
Outputs	Detailed reports on current situation annually.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systematic data collection and percentage monitoring among students, PhDs, academic and administrative staff, related to gender, age, socioeconomic status, disabilities; - Analysis of the data collected in respect to gender balance in leadership and decision making, gender equality in recruitment and career progression, work-life balance, social inclusiveness of the institution.
Impact	Improving analysing system and introducing a monitoring framework to prevent and detect problems.

UNISOFIA - Action 5	
Action title	Expansion of the University's Center for Psychological Counselling and Research;
Key objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To establish a safe and supportive university environment for everyone who has faced GBV; - To provide psychological and social tools for overcoming trauma and negative experiences.
Thematic area	Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age, ethnicity, sexual orientation

Intersectoral component	Yes: should there be In cases where there is a need for specific psychological help/follow-up therapy and treatment, the Center will draw from a network of external partners such as the Bulgarian Association for Family Therapy, the Bulgarian Association for Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy, the Center for outpatient treatment "Adaptation", the Center for Psychological Health & Prevention, Military Medical Academy- Sofia and the Psychiatric Clinic, Aleksanrovska Hospital, for example.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	- Engagement of professional experts
Audience	- University employees; - University Students.
Activities	Include additional counselling topics, specifically related to combating GBV. Promote of the service.
Time-frame	To begin in 2025 (exact date to be confirmed).
Outputs	- Creating a safe and supportive university environment for everyone who has faced GBV; - Providing psychological and social tools for overcoming traumas and negative experience and for successfully re-integrating into the working/ education process/space.
Outcomes	- The services of the University's Center for Psychological Counselling and Research specifically related to combating GBV will be improved; - The services of the University's Center for Psychological Counselling and Research specifically related to combating GBV will be improved; - Increased awareness and use of the University's Center for Psychological Counselling and Research as a unit within the university that provides psychological counseling, support and assistance for individuals who experience GBV.
Impact	Improved mental health of staff and students.

4.4 Le Mans University

UM - Action 1	
Action title	Influence of biases in decision-making
Key objective	Tackling biases in recruitment
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Ethnicity, age, disability, gender, religion/belief, sexual orientation, nationality, socioeconomic status.

Intersectoral component	Yes, professional trainers.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human capital (NEXUS staff, if needed professional staff to deliver training to be hired); - Working hours; - Budget; - Technical tools.
Audience	Recruiters: people involved in hiring, specifically in the screening and the evaluation processes.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Submit a survey to the potential audience to understand biases in all trio institutions; - Design the training course in May 2025 (the survey will be developed collaboratively within the trio group); - Design the content of the course from June 2024 to August 2024 (tasks will be divided among the trio partners); - Find participants for the courses in September 2024; - Deliver the course (online/ in person) in December; - Evaluate the skills and content achieved within December
Time-frame	From June 2024 to January 2025.
Outputs	A training (online/presence) course in English about the biases that affect the recruitment process.
Outcomes	50 recruiters in total (approximately) will be trained (10 from Serbia, 20 from France, 20 from Italy).
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased transparency and objectivity in the recruitment process; - People selected for positions in the university without any discrimination and biases in the selection/hiring process.

UM - Action 2	
Action title	Gender+ dimension in research
Key objective	A Gender+ Approach in the Research Fields
Thematic area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, socioeconomic status, age, disability, nationality, ethnicity/race, religion/belief, sexual orientation
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No

Inputs	People, time, material (pedagogical), technological tool.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers; - Academic staff.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meet with project officers of the three partners to receive input on this topic. Share the inputs to create the guidelines within July 2024. - State-of-the-art guidelines and toolkits already exist. Create a SharePoint with the trio and organise a meeting together within July 2024. - Co-create and develop guidelines (with project officers from the trio partner institutions) about gender+ in research applications. Examples from different research disciplines will be included in the guidelines (workload will be divided among the trio from August to December 2024). - Review of the guidelines with scientists. - Share the guidelines on internal platforms.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - December 2024: first draft; - Spring 2025: final draft.
Outputs	Guidelines about including a gender+ dimension in EU-funded research in English will be produced.
Outcomes	50 people from the trio group institutions will be aware of the importance of gender+ issues in research.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers will be increasingly sensitive to the importance of including a gender+ approach; - Improved skills among researchers; - The gender+ dimension will be implemented in research proposals/ developing grants.

UM - Action 3	
Action title	Parenting Resource Group
Key objective	Design open call for Community Builders
Thematic area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Parental/family status
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal staff; - Materials for the group.
Audience	All parents in the institution.

Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise a meeting with all the institution's parents to talk about creating a parenting resource group. Find at least two members who could be community builders; - A call to action for parents to become community builder within, after the meeting; - Identifying the members that are willing to become community builders.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - September 2024: Find potential community builders; - September - October 2024: Call to action; - November 2024: Identify community builders; - By the of 2024: meeting and call to action completed.
Outputs	Parenting Resource Group.
Outcomes	10 people engaged in parenting issues (e.g., the parenting resource group).
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parenthood is understood as being a part of the organisational culture. - Improved engagement by people regarding parenting and work life balance.

UM - Action 4	
Action title	Fostering empowerment for women at work
Key objective	To give women more opportunities to develop their careers at university
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Socioeconomic status, age, disability, nationality, ethnicity/race, religion/belief, sexual orientation, gender identity.
Intersectoral component	Yes, external stakeholders: Professionals to organise negotiation training
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	Internal staff and internal resources (venue, material, etc) / expert in the field of the activity
Audience	Staff members, students
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inventory of existing information and training: meeting with the training department and the University Information, Orientation and Professional Integration Service; - Set up a training-workshop program for University staff (single-sex) and work with the University Information, Orientation and Professional Integration Service and external partners to set up training for female students; - Promote mentoring; - Evaluate new skills.
Time-frame	June - December 2024

Outputs	Two workshops; two negotiation trainings.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A better understanding of the professional context, career development, promotion and training opportunities for university employees; - Keys to negotiating entry into the job market for young graduates.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase in the number of women in category A and in the number of female incumbents; - Better integration of young female graduates into the workforce, with a job corresponding to their level of education.

UM - Action 5	
Action title	Gender, health and well-being
Key objective	To have a better understanding of physical and mental health issues among women and LGBTQIA+ people at the university.
Thematic area	Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, religion/belief, age.
Intersectoral component	Yes, external stakeholders such as associations (for LGBTQIA+ people, or feminist associations) will be involved with this action.
Relevance for data collection	Yes: data will be collected to evaluate the current situation with a view to informing and to adapting health and well-being supports at the institution.
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human resource/time from: - Personal disability referent / student disability referent; - Health center psychologist; - Health prevention officer; Equality officer; - Inclusion and anti-discrimination referent; - Student representatives; - External associations.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students; - Staff members.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a working group focusing on specific themes for example: menstrual leave, trans-identity, sexual orientation, disabling pathologies (endometriosis); - Conduct an inventory of needs and of existing facilities; - Inform staff and students of their rights by disseminating best practices; - Evaluate the action.
Time-frame	June - December 2024
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One active working group;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good practices guide.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify specific problems encountered by women and by LBGTQIA+ people; and possible solutions; - Identify possible solutions to the problems encountered by women and by LBGTQIA+ people.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The well-being of women and of LBGTQIA+ people at university will be improved; - The rights of LBGTQIA+ people will be recognised and promoted therefore challenging stereotypes and discrimination against this group.

4.5 Bay Zoltán

BZN - Action 1	
Action title	E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality
Key objective	Create an e-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality; Equality and diversity in research.
Thematic area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
Level of co-design	Twin trio: this action was co-designed within the trio group and was based on an already implemented individual pilot activity of AGH. An intersectional component and localisation was designed within the trio. The e-course will be translated and a context sensitive approach will be incorporated to the course as the cultural and organisational context of each partner institute differs.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity.
Intersectoral component	Yes: the Hungarian Agency for Research and Innovation as a research funder and as evaluators for possible future implementation on the national/ regional level will be involved in this action.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polish version of the e-course; - Course content including infographics, charts, data, activities, quizzes and cases; - Translation localisation; - Redesign; - Implementation.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers; - Support staff; - PhD students; - Research agency in Hungary (NKFIH).
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare the files for translation; - Translate the documents and graphics into ENGLISH;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Context-specific activities: identify the areas where local adaptations are necessary; - Intersectionality: identify areas where various sectoral dimensions are not addressed sufficiently; - Redesigning and replacing the content according to localisation and intersectional analysis; - Implementation of the e-course on e-learning platforms; - Recruitment of users/ participants; - Evaluation.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May - June 2024: Initial review for intersectional aspects by AGH; - July - August 2024: Translate into English by AGH; - September 2024: Release the course for the partners in English - September 2024: Discuss intersectional dimension (combined with Cyprus SV); - October 2024: Implementation of changes in the English course; - November 2024: E-course ready for launch.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One English version of the course 2.0 (with intersectional changes); - One Hungarian version of the course 2.0 (with intersectional changes); - One Polish version of the course 2.0 (with intersectional changes).
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers will be able to consider gender, ethnicity, age etc. dimensions in designing and executing their research; - Researchers will be able to recruit more diverse and more equal team members; - Support staff will be able to draw attention to imbalances and inform the researchers about opportunities brought by including diverse practices in research design.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased awareness of diversity and equality in designing and conducting research; - Better understanding of how to incorporate gender, age, ethnicity etc. dimensions in research.

BZN - Action 2	
Action title	Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring (GEAM) Tool
Key objective	Gather data from the GEAM Survey every three years; To map the situation regarding GE in the three Institutions; To create an updated database for each Institution; Be able to make comparisons, keep track of changes, improvements or pitfalls.
Thematic area	Data collection processes
Level of co-design	Both at the FredU Open Labs and in the twin trio groups. Each partner will decide which sections of the GEAM tool will be used and included in the survey. The Joint Action suggests that the GEAM Tool is implemented every three years in the Institutions. For AGH and Bay Zoltan this is a new Action. For Frederick it will be the second time to implement the tool. The tool is offered in English. Polish and Greek. Some sections of the questionnaire will not be

	used by all as the questionnaire addresses many areas. The newest version of the tool includes questions for the administrative staff.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, other minority identities.
Intersectoral component	Yes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The GEAM Tool is designed by external stakeholders; - An external stakeholder from the (HUN-REN Hungarian Research Network) will be involved with the translated survey; - For the Hungarian translation and implementation of the translated survey, collaboration with the “Act on Gender” team and other interested Hungarian universities (two identified at the moment) will take place.
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	Questionnaire: A survey in English, Hungarian, Polish and Greek including questions/items regarding: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruitment and Promotion; - Training; - Work-life Balance; - Parental Leave; - Covid; - Organisational Culture and Climate: GE and Working Culture; - Bullying, Harassment and Microaggressions.
Audience	Faculty and/or Staff of each institution.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact the owners of the questionnaire; - Activate the survey; - Contact the authorities of each institution to distribute the questionnaire; - Send the survey to faculty and/or staff; - Get the results.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024: Finalise the decision and contact the owners of the questionnaire; - July - August 2024: Review and decide which questions are to be included in the questionnaire; - September - October 2024: Discussions with the authorities of each Institutions; - October 2024: Translate the survey; - January - February 2025: Administer the survey; - March - April 2025: Retrieve and analyse the results; - Repeat every three years.
Outputs	Results on the current situation of GE in each Institution.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to map and monitor the GE situation in every university; - Ability to minimise gaps and inequalities; - Evaluate the progress in GE.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase awareness of GE; - Make gender inequalities visible; - Allow faculty and staff to express themselves anonymously;

	- Allow policy makers to make informed decisions.
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BZN - Action 3	
Action title	Inclusive Communication Guidelines
Key objective	To design guidelines to make communication within and outside the institution fairer and more inclusive; Enhance competences: knowledge, skills and attitudes; To provide the community with a practical guidance on communication patterns for inclusive language; Setting standards for internal and external communication; Sharing best practices/lessons learned and support mutual learning among the Trio.
Thematic area	Work-life balance and organisational culture Gender balance in leadership and decision making Gender equality in recruitment and career progression Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Twin trio. A section will be dedicated for guidelines in Polish for AGH; Inclusion of internal stakeholders (AGH: cooperation with students). FredU and BZN will have the document in English only.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, sexual orientation, age, ethnicity & race, religion & belief, disability, mental health & neurodiversity
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	- Personal workload of internal and external experts as well as students on inclusive language, editing and writing; - Digital document with a user-friendly layout.
Audience	University's community: employees and students, External stakeholders (other universities, research agencies, companies collaborating with the university, NGOs).
Activities	- Students desk research (AGH); - Short interviews with staff and students (AGH); - Content development based on the above (shared task); - Final editing of the Guidelines (shared task); - Publish the Guidelines (shared task).
Time-frame	- May - June 2024: Students desk research (AGH); - June - September 2024: Short interviews with staff and students (AGH); - September 2024: Discuss the progress and status in Cyprus during the second study visit; - October - December 2024: Content development by sharing the work among the three institutions; - February 2025: Publication.
Outputs	- Resources of the desk research used as references;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidelines to be used in the official communication of the university/research organisation internally and externally, between academics/administrative staff but also with students. A digital document with user-friendly layout.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workshop for the Trio on sharing good practices and knowledge transfer in inclusive communication; - Enhancement of professional and personal communication: for example, oral and written communication; - A more inclusive work and study environment.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal and external communication at BZN are improved. Make communication fairer and more inclusive. Enhanced communication competences; - Enhanced communication standards.

BZN - Action 4	
Action title	Fostering participation in work-related trainings through data collection with a gender+ perspective
Key objective	Data collection and analysis to map the situation and establish the short-term trends of the participation of staff in professional trainings by gender and other inequality areas.
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Both BZN Open Labs and twin trio.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age; position within the organisation (including managerial pos.); Additional focus on underrepresented groups, as revealed by the statistics.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	Statistics (data) of training participation of different groups; Satisfaction rates of trainings
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All employees; - Underrepresented groups.
Activities	Intervening by filling the gaps mentioned as obstacles to participation in training; Providing training bonus; Promoting trainings
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two years (first implementation in 2025, covering the period 2023-2024); - In correlation with the annual training plans of the institution; - Gather data in February - April 2025; - Analyse data in May - July 2025.
Outputs	Analysis of data of training participation of different groups Recommendations.

Outcomes	Preparing interventions (actions) based on the results of the data collection. Making trainings more accessible for underrepresented groups within the organisation.
Impact	Revealing discrimination instances and possible blind spots. Making the institution more inclusive.

BZN - Action 5	
Action title	Eliminating prejudices, improving corporate culture - everyone is important!
Key objective	Implementing an attitude formation programme via equal opportunity training
Thematic area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age; schooling; job position and unit of employment within the organisation
Intersectoral component	Yes: trainers (NGOs) for the sensitisation and the equal opportunities content; partner RPOs to present institutional good practices (invited from the project stakeholder database).
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	Staff time invested; training organisation costs; support from management (including middle management)
Audience	Employees and management (basic training for both staff and managers, but in separate groups)
Activities	<p>Training sessions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of compassion and empathy (what it feels like to be discriminated against) and what can be done with it; - Role exchange training, where people conduct out each other's tasks as far as data protection allows; - Trying out gender roles, experiential learning (e.g. construction task with constant interruptions); - Finding more about each other using Undercover information sessions (both professional and personal sides involved); - Taking into account the situation of colleagues who commute/live further away when organising the programme.
Time-frame	Two years.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stronger team cohesion; - Increased employee retainment (lower staff turnover); - Burnout prevention; - Efficiency increased through higher collaboration; - Less conflict.

Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 1/3 of total staff included in the programme within two years; - Overall job satisfaction improved by at least 5%; - Measurement included in the annual staff satisfaction survey.
Impact	Prejudice will be decreased in the organisation.

4.6 AGH University of Kraków

AGH - Action 1	
Action title	E-course on Gender Equality and Intersectionality
Key objective	Create/Improve an e-course with Gender Equality and Intersectionality approach; Equality and diversity in research.
Thematic area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
Level of co-design	Twin trio. Intersectional component and localisation is designed with the trio; The e-course will be translated and localised which requires individual approach as cultural and organisational context of the partners is different.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity.
Intersectoral component	Yes. Polish Research Agencies as evaluators for possible future implementation on the national/ regional level). An external stakeholder from a research centre (National Science Centre in Poland) will be involved in the testing and evaluation of the course.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polish version of the e-course; - Course content including infographics, charts, data, activities, quizzes and cases; - Work-load: translation localisation, redesign, implementation.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers; - Support staff; - PhD students; - Students; - Research agencies in Poland (NCN, NCBiR, NAWA).
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation of the files for translation; - Translating the documents and graphics into ENGLISH. Localisation activities: identification of the areas where localisation is necessary; - Intersectionality: identifying areas where various sectoral dimensions are not addressed sufficiently; - Redesigning and replacing the content according to localisation and intersectional analysis; - Implementation of the e-course on e-learning platforms; - Recruitment of users/ participants; - Evaluation.

Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May - June: 2024 Initial review for intersectional aspects by AGH; - July - August 2024: Translation into English by AGH; - 1 September 2024: Release the course for the partners in ENG; - September 2024: Intersectional dimension (combined with Cyprus SV); - November 2024: Recommendations for changes in ENG course; - December 2024: Implement the recommendations in EN version of the e-course; - January 2025: Recruitment of the participants.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One English version of the course 2.0 (with intersectional changes).
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers will be able to consider gender, ethnicity, age dimensions in designing and executing their research; - Researchers will be able to recruit more diverse and more equal team members; - Support staff will be able to draw attention to imbalances and inform the researchers about opportunities brought by diversity practices in research design; - Awareness on Inclusion and GE.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased awareness towards diversity and equality in designing and conducting research with the view to intersectionality; - Better understanding of gender, age, ethnicity dimensions in research; - Student and staff can have access for awareness and educational purposes.

AGH - Action 2	
Action title	Implementation of the Gender Equality Auditing and Monitoring Tool
Key objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gather data from the GEAM Survey; - To map the situation regarding GEP in AGHL; - To create an updated database for each institution; - Be able to make comparisons, keep track of changes, improvements or pitfalls.
Thematic area	Data collection processes related to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work life balance and organisational culture; - Gender equality and career progression; - Gender balance in leadership and decision making; - Measures against gender base violence, including sexual harassment.
Level of co-design	Both FredU Open Labs and twin trio. Each partner will decide which sections of the GEAM tool will be used and included in the survey. The Joint Action suggests that the GEAM Tool is implemented in the three institutions. For AGH and BAY-Zoltan is a new Action. For Frederick it will be the second time to implement the tool. The tool is offered in English. Polish and Greek. Some sections of the questionnaire will not be used by all as the questionnaire addresses many areas. Its newest version includes questions for the administrative staff and Students.

Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, other minority identities.
Intersectoral component	Yes. The GEAM Tool is designed by external stakeholders. An external stakeholder from a research centre (National Science Centre) will be involved in the consultation of the research tool.
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	Questionnaire. A survey in English, Polish and Greek on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recruitment and Promotion; - Training; - Work-life Balance; - Parental leave; - Organisational Culture and Climate: GE and Working Culture; - Bullying, Harassment and Microaggressions.
Audience	Faculty and Staff & Students of each institution
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact the owners of the questionnaire; - Activate the survey; - Contact the authorities of each institution to distribute the questionnaire; - Send the survey to faculty and/or staff & students; - Get the results.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024: Finalise the decision and contact the owners of the questionnaire to create user accounts; - July - August 2024: Review and decide which questions to be included in the questionnaire; - September 2024: Discussions with the authorities of each Institutions; - October 2024: Launch the survey; - November 2004: Retrieve the results.
Outputs	Results on the current situation of GE in each Institution.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to map and monitor the GE situation in every university; Able to minimise gaps and inequalities. Map the current situation the progress in GE at AGH.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor data in AGH; - Increase awareness on GE; - Make gender inequalities visible; - Allow faculty and staff to express themselves anonymously; - Allow policy makers to make informed decisions.

AGH - Action 3	
Action title	Inclusive communication guidelines

Key objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design guidelines to make communication within and outside the university fairer and more inclusive; - Enhance competences: knowledge, skills and attitudes; - To provide the community with a practical guidance on communication patterns for inclusive language; - Setting standards for internal and external communication; - Sharing best practices/lessons learned and support mutual learning among the trio.
Thematic area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture - Gender balance in leadership and decision making - Gender equality in recruitment and career progression - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Twin trio. A section will be dedicated for guidelines in Polish for AGH; Inclusion of internal stakeholders (AGH: cooperation with students). FredU and BZN will have the document in English only.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, sexual orientation, age, ethnicity & race, religion & belief, disability, mental health & neurodiversity.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	Personal workload of internal and external experts as well as students on inclusive language, editing and writing
Audience	University's community: employees and students, external stakeholders (other universities, research agencies, companies collaborating with the university, NGOs).
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students desk research (AGH); - Short interviews with staff and students (AGH); - Content development based on the above (shared); - Final editing of the Guidelines (shared); - Publication of the Guidelines (shared)
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May - June 2024: Students desk research (AGH); - June - September 2024: Short interviews with staff and students (AGH); - September 2024: Discuss the progress and status in Cyprus during the second study visit; - October - December 2024: Content development by sharing the work among the three institutions; - February 2025: publication.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidelines to be used in the official communication of the university/research organisation internally and externally, between academics/administrative staff but also with students; - A digital document with user-friendly layout.

Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workshop for the trio on sharing good practices and transfer knowledge in inclusive communication; - Enhancement of the professional and personal communication: oral and written; - More inclusive work and study environment.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the internal and external communication of the institution; - Make communication fairer and more inclusive; - Enhanced communication competences; - Enhanced communication standards.

AGH - Action 3	
Action title	Fostering participation in work-related trainings through data collection with a gender+ perspective
Key objective	Data collection and analysis to map the situation and establish the short-term trends of the participation of staff in professional trainings by gender and other inequality areas.
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Both BZN Open Labs and twin trio.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age; position within the organisation (including managerial pos.); type of courses.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statistical (data) of training participation of different groups; - Established variables for data; - Data from the Services of the University.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All employees; - Underrepresented groups specified in the analysis.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing variables for collecting data; - Extract the data from the database, taking into account the last three full years; - Conducting the analysis; - Follow-up with actions to ensure more inclusivity (specific to the institution).
Time-frame	Three academic years; Statistical analysis annually, in correlation with the annual training plans of the institution. Analyse data for the years 2022-2023, 2023-2024, 2024-2025.
Outputs	Analysis of inequalities/gaps of participation regarding the dimensions of inclusiveness (a report).

Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparing interventions (actions) based on the results of the data collection; - Making trainings more accessible for underrepresented groups within the organisation.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revealing discrimination instances and possible blind spots; - Making trainings more accessible to various employee groups, making the institution more inclusive

AGH - Action 4	
Action title	GEP information campaign
Key objective	To raise awareness about GEP, to increase visibility
Thematic area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Work-life balance and organisational culture; - Measures against GBV including sexual harassment.
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	<p>Gender identity, sexual orientation, people with disabilities, age.</p> <p>The information campaign will have the objective of communicating the GEP rationale to the wider community. As AGH collected (and will continue to collect?) data beyond gender dimension, “storytelling of the data” will include also age and disability</p>
Intersectoral component	Yes, an external stakeholder from a marketing agency will be involved in the preparation of some of the social media campaign activities.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experts; - Trainers; - Outsourced description of the procedures; - Financial resources; - Infrastructure.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AGH community; - Employee; - Students.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design of the Information campaign together with the Media Centre; - Set up of a work group; - Selection of the marketing channels; - Brainstorming of the actions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Information in each Internal Newsletter (4000+ employees) and Students Newsletter (20 000 students); o Production of the marketing materials (promotional video, podcast); o Online meeting under the initiative “bunkier Nauki” (Bunker of science: regular meetings with scientists conducted in a less

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> formal way); ○ Display in an internal TV; ○ Publication of the information on AGH's intranet in a section for HR; ○ Compulsory trainings for the executive/ head of units (academics + administration). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation of the information snippets according to the media selected (social media, bulletins, internal TV): text and graphics; - Execution of the information campaign; - Evaluation of the campaign.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May 2024 - September 2024: Preparation of the information snippets according to the media selected (social media, bulletins, internal TV): text and graphics; - June 2024: Promotion of the institution of the Ombudsman (leaflets, banners) during event for employees on AGH; - August - October 2024: Creation and execution of the information campaign together with the Media Centre; - June 2025: Evaluation of the campaign.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posters, billboards, social media reels; - More cases of abuse or violation reported in the short-term; - Decrease of the number of cases of abuse or violation reported in the long-term; - Higher employee retention rate; - Increased work satisfaction; - Increased response rate for the GEP 2025 surveys; - Information snippets in June, September, October, November and December 2024 (5 items): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ One infographic based on GEP to be used in internal TV; ○ One article in Newsletter for Employees. - One article in Students' Newsletter.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness on Inclusion and GE; - Increased awareness about GEP at the university; - Increased awareness about intersectional dimension of GEP; - Enhanced knowledge about GEP2.0 areas.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve knowledge and awareness on equality, counteracting inequalities within AGH structures (among scientists, administration and students); - Increase of the trust towards GEP policy; - Demystifying the GEP; - Information about the GEP's rationale; - Better understanding of the GEP's aims; - Greater visibility of the GEP.

4.7 Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Niš

UN - Action 1	
Action title	Influence of biases in decision-making

Key objective	Tackling biases in recruitment
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Socioeconomic status, age, gender identity, disability, nationality, ethnicity/race, religion/belief, sexual orientation.
Intersectoral component	Yes, an external stakeholder (from the National Employment Service) will hold a workshop on avoiding bias in employment.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human capital (NEXUS staff, if needed hire a professional staff to deliver training); - Working hours; - Budget; - Technical tool.
Audience	Recruiters: people involved in the screening and the evaluation processes.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May 2024: Submit a survey to the potential audience to understand their biases to design the training course; - June - August 2024: Design the content of the course from June to August 2024; - September 2024: Find the participants for the courses, sending the invitation with the registration form and having the participants; - December 2024: Deliver the course (online/presence), evaluate the skills and content achieved.
Time-frame	June 2024 - January 2025.
Outputs	A training course, about the biases that affect the recruitment process.
Outcomes	A sample of recruiters trained, around 50 people in total (10 from Serbia, 20 from France, 20 from Italy).
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More transparency and objectivity in the recruitment process; - To select people without any discrimination and biases.

UN - Action 2	
Action title	Gender+ dimension in research
Key objective	A Gender + Approach in the Research Fields
Thematic area	Research and teaching content
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Socioeconomic status, age, disability, nationality, ethnicity/race, religion/belief, sexual orientation

Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People; - Time; - Material (pedagogical); - Technological tool.
Audience	Researchers and academic staff
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - July 2024: Meet with project officers of the three partners to receive input on this topic. Share the inputs to create the guidelines; - July: State-of-the-art guidelines and toolkits already exist. Create a SharePoint with the trio and organise a meeting together. - August - December 2024: Develop guidelines about gender+ in research applications and co-creating with project officers of the three partners. Include examples in different research domains. Divide de workload among the trio. - November 2024: Review of the guidelines with scientists. - February 2025: Share the guidelines on internal platform.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First draft: by December 2024. • Final draft: Spring 2025, before the NEXUS final report.
Outputs	Guidelines about gender+ dimension EU founded research in English.
Outcomes	50 people among the trio are aware of gender+ issues in research.
Impact	Make research gender+ sensitive. Improved skills of the scientists. The gender+ dimension has been implemented in the research proposals/developing grant skills.

UN - Action 3	
Action title	Parenting Resource Group
Key objective	Design open call for Community Builders
Thematic area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Family/parental status.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	Internal staff and materials
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All parents in the institution.

Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - September 2024: Organise a meeting with all the institution's parents to talk about creating a parenting resource group. Find at least two members who could be community builders. - September - October 2024: A call to action for parents to become community builders, after the meeting. - November 2024: Identifying the members that are willing to become community builders.
Time-frame	End of 2024: meeting and call to action.
Outputs	Parenting Resource Group
Outcomes	10 people are engaged in parenting issues (meeting and resource group)
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parenthood is a recognised part of the organisation's culture. - Improvement of the engagement of people on parenting and work life balance theme.

UN - Action 4	
Action title	Informing employees and students about the existence of the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment at MFN (RonPPfromSH)
Key objective	Raise awareness about sexual harassment
Thematic area	Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender identity, ethnicity/race, sexual orientation
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Yes, collecting data about number of informed employees and students about the existence of the Regulation on Prevention and Protection from Sexual Harassment at MFN.
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepared the notification on RonPPfromSH, - Printing materials (document on RonPPfromSH) - Preparation and processing of survey forms (work hours)
Audience	Students during enrolment and employees when signing employment contracts or work engagements.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preparation of the notification on RonPPfromSH, - Posting the RonPPfromSH document on the faculty's website, - Distribution of the document via email to all employees and students, - Distribution of the document as a hard copy to students when enrolling and to newly employees when signing an employment contract, - Announcement of the telephone number of the RR Commission, - Keeping records of the number of views on the faculty's website.

	- Survey analysis.
Time-frame	Every year during enrolment for the semester and when signing contracts or contract amendments.
Outputs	Number of distributed documents, number of website views, survey analysis.
Outcomes	All employees and students informed.
Impact	Creating an informed environment for students and employees by informing them about the regulation and the measures against sexual harassment and for the prevention of gender-based discrimination.

UN - Action 5	
Action title	Better environment for Roma students at the faculty
Key objective	Increase the number of Roma students at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering Nis
Thematic area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Ethnicity
Intersectoral component	Yes, close cooperation with an external stakeholder from the Roma NGO.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human resources; - Budget for dorm scholarship.
Audience	4-year high school students of the Roma population, NGOs (e.g. REF), faculty staff.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A general announcement on the faculty's website in the Romani language; - During the annual promotion of the faculty in high schools with Roma students, include our faculty student of Roma nationality to talk about the advantages of studying MF; - Cooperation and promotion with the Roma NGO (REF), once a year; - One scholarship for the costs of a student dormitory for a student of Roma nationality.
Time-frame	Three to five years.
Outputs	Website and social media announcements, agreement signed with REF.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased Roma students by 30%; - Increased number of Roma engineers.

Impact	- Increased number of Roma students at the faculty beyond the government quotas for Roma students
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4.8 Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia

IIT - Action 1	
Action title	How to handle harassment in the workplace
Key objective	Wellbeing in the workplace
Thematic area	Measures against GBV including sexual violence
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Disability, nationality, ethnicity/race, and gender identity.
Intersectoral component	Yes. The external stakeholders that joined our Open Labs will be involved. They are both research organisations well-known in the Italian panorama. They have been engaged in the Nexus project also for the Open Labs and were involved, during the Open Lab, in the codesign of the action focused on the harassment in the workplace.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal staff and internal resources (venue, material, etc.); - Expert in the field of the activity (only if necessary).
Audience	Directors, manager, and people with leadership/mentorship roles
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Survey to inquire about interests and define participants for the first training; - Choose and define the training content and the expert (only if necessary); - Plan the schedule, transports, materials and the venue; - Deliver the course; - Evaluate the skills acquired.
Time-frame	May 2024 - December 2024.
Outputs	In-person training/online (it depends from the audience) course where theoretical moments on the topic alternate with practical case workshops.
Outcomes	Approximately 20 IIT managers are trained about to the topic of harassment in the workplace, and aware of the importance of promoting a culture of respect and difference within their work team.
Impact	The issue of harassment in the workplace is an anchor part of the IIT institution's organisational culture and work well-being.

IIT - Action 2	
Action title	Designing ways to collect non-binary data
Key objective	Data collection
Thematic area	Data collection processes
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness to diverse gender identities and inclusion, with a particular focus on non-binary people; - Respect for best practices in gender diversity.
Intersectoral component	Not necessarily - Consulting by IT experts (only if necessary)
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IIT internal staff for management adaptation and cross-functional flow development; - Support and involvement of staff from HR functions, Project Office and Data Analysis, ICT, GDPR, DPO, TTO, Communication; - Consulting by IT experts (only if necessary).
Audience	Department/Offices: HR, ROD - DATA ANALYSIS, GDPR, DPO, ICT, ROD – Project Office, Communication Directorate and Technology Transfer
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of needs and available technical resources (gathering availability technical table participation); - Analysis of non-binary subject data collection and how it can be integrated into IIT data; - Construction of cross-functional flow for collection and integration of non-binary subject data from new hired and from the active work-force; - 4) Collection of information from outside and definition of the flow from inside.
Time-frame	May - December 2024.
Outputs	New flow for collection and integration of data related to non-binary Subjects.
Outcomes	Integration of non-binary subject data collection into IIT's data collection Process.
Impact	Increased awareness of the institute's staff according to the categories of diversity.

IIT - Action 3	
Action title	Influence of biases in decision-making
Key objective	Tackling biases in recruitment

Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	The specific dimensions addressed by the actions will be gender identity, age, disability, nationality, socio-economic status.
Intersectoral component	Yes. An external stakeholder will be involved. They will be involved in designing or checking the content of the activities.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human capital (NEXUS staff, if needed hire a professional staff to deliver training); - Working hours; - Budget; - Technical tool.
Audience	Recruiters: people involved in the screening and the evaluation processes.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May 2024: Submit a survey to the potential audience to understand their biases to design the training course; - June - August 2024: Design the content of the course; - Find the participants for the courses within September 2024: sending the invitation with the registration form and having the participants; - Deliver the course (online/presence) within December 2024. - Evaluate the skills and content achieved within December 2024.
Time-frame	June 2024 - January 2025.
Outputs	A training (online/presence) course, in English, about the biases that affect the recruitment process.
Outcomes	A sample of recruiters trained, around 50 people in total (10 from Serbia, 20 from France, 20 from Italy).
Impact	More transparency and objectivity in the recruitment process. The purpose is to select people without any discrimination and biases.

IIT - Action 4	
Action title	Gender+ dimension in research
Key objective	A Gender + Approach in the Research Fields
Thematic area	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	We will design guidelines oriented to the promotion of gender+ approach in the IIT research domains, gender will be the main dimension with an intersectional approach through disability, age, and socio-economic status.

Intersectoral component	Yes. IIT will engage some of its external stakeholders in the research field. IIT would like to engage them in the design/checking of the content for the guidelines.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People; - Time; - Material (pedagogical); - Technological too;
Audience	Researchers and academic staff
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meeting with project officers of the three partners to receive input on this topic. Share the inputs to create the guidelines within July - State-of-the-art guidelines and toolkits already exist. Create a SharePoint with the trio and organise a meeting together within July. - Develop guidelines about gender+ in research applications and co-creating with project officers of the three partners. Include examples in different research domains. Divide the workload among the trio, from August to December 2024. - Review of the guidelines with scientists within November 2024. - Share the guidelines on internal platforms within February 2025
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First draft: by December 2024. - Final draft: spring 2025, before the NEXUS final report.
Outputs	Guidelines about gender+ dimension EU funded research in English.
Outcomes	50 people among the trio are aware of gender+ issues in research
Impact	Make research gender+ sensitive. Improved skills of the scientists. The gender+ dimension has been implemented in the research proposals/developing grant skills.

IIT - Action 5	
Action title	Parenting Resource Group
Key objective	Design open call for Community Builders
Thematic area	Work-life balance and organisational culture
Level of co-design	Twin trio
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Age and parental/family status.
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	No

Inputs	Internal staff and materials.
Audience	All parents in the institution.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organise a meeting with all the institution's parents to talk about creating a parenting resource group. Find at least two members who could be community builders, in September 2024. - A call to action for parents to become community builders in September - October, after the meeting. - Finding the members that are willing to become community builders, in November.
Time-frame	- September 2024 to December 2024.
Outputs	Parenting Resource Group.
Outcomes	10 people are engaged in parenting issues (meeting and resource group).
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parenthood is a recognised part of the organisation's culture. - Improvement of engagement on the theme of parenting and work-life balance.

4.9 Koç University

KU - Action 1	
Action title	GBV Training and Awareness Online Module
Key objective	Develop a skill and knowledge-based online module to educate and raise awareness on GBV and provide strategies to both deal with and to combat it in partner institutions and beyond.
Thematic area	Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Twin trio. It was fully designed within the trio. UNISOFIA are going to develop module including the IT part and the involvement of a teaching specialist + 1 project representative for the content structuring. with input from the partner institutions. Specifically, UNISOFIA can deal with the development of the module - the IT part and the involvement of a teaching specialist + 1 project representative for the content structuring. TUD has shared materials from the various programmes and trainings that they currently have in progress regarding GBV. Uni Sofia will monitor this online module and have oversight of the periodical update of the modules content. The graphic design of the module will be based on KU's previous campaign against GBV, zone campaign (https://zone.ku.edu.tr/).
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Sex and gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, nationality, race & ethnicity, (inclusiveness beyond gender will be institute specific).
Intersectoral component	Yes
Relevance for data collection	No

Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design time; - Collating the module materials; - The module platform will need to be organised.
Audience	Staff and students throughout partner institutes and beyond
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create module content; - Create platform to host module; - Develop networks to disseminate the module through; - Launch module.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - June 2024: begin building the module; - Release module on 25 November 2024 (this is the international day against sexual violence).
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 30 people per partner institution will have completed the module by February 2025; - The quality of the module will be measured by post module evaluation completed by individuals who have taken the course.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals in the partner institutions and beyond will have access to the online module; - Increased awareness and understanding of GBV; - Increased visibility of NEXUS project.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The module will include an assessment of individuals understanding and awareness of GBV; - Online module about GBV will improve awareness and understanding of what GBV; - Online module about GBV will provide strategies and information how about to deal with experiences of GBV (observed & experienced personally); - An online module about GBV will be a resource for those working in the partner institutions (and beyond) to improve their practice. - The high-quality design of the module will have great impact in terms of visibility and dissemination of both NEXUS project and its measures against GBV in higher education

KU - Action 2	
Action title	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis
Key objective	To ascertain the base line needs in relation mentoring in the partner institutions and to subsequently develop a mentoring programme.
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression
Level of co-design	Twin trio. It was fully designed within the trio. UNISOFIA has an online tool as part of an international mentoring program (https://mentoring.euraxess.bg/) that is currently available at UNISOFIA. This tool can be shared and used by KU and TU Dublin (and in time with the other NEXUS partners). The tool will be filled with content and adapted to the specific needs of the partner

	institutions.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender (including gender identity); disability; race & ethnicity; nationality; age; family status
Intersectoral component	No
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Person/persons to construct the survey to be compiled; - Teams from each university to administer the survey; - Teams from each university to analyse the survey data; - Person/persons to compile a report on the findings of the survey.
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential mentors and potential mentees. - Special focus will be on early career women researchers (including doctoral students and post docs)
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Construct survey; - Administer survey; - Analyse results; - Disseminate results via each institution's website.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 June - 30 September 2024: Construct the survey; - 1 October - 15 November 2024: Administer the survey; - 15 November - 15 December 2024: Analysis of survey; - An infographic on survey results will be disseminated via social media on 11 February 2025, Day of Women and Girls in Science, thus increasing the visibility of NEXUS project and mentoring needs of women in science.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Completed surveys (60 people minimum per institution to complete the survey); - Report on survey findings.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Baseline needs assessment in relation to mentorship will be conducted; - A mentoring training programme (manual) will be developed.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each institution will have increased understanding of what skills mentors need to be effective mentors; - Each institution will have increased understanding of what mentees need to advance their careers in a holistic, supportive and quality manner.

KU - Action 3	
Action title	Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression and Success
Key objective	To develop a training programme/manual for mentors with inclusivity at its core using the data gathered in the action "Inclusive Mentoring for Career Progression - a Needs Analysis".
Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

Level of co-design	Twin trio, the action be implemented by all components of the trio. UniSofia are already involved with a mentoring programme so, for them this action will mean adapting their current mentoring programme so as to make it more inclusive. TU Dublin also has a mentoring programme in place and via consultation with 'People Development' the current programme will ensure that mentors have increased awareness and understanding of inclusivity/intersectional issues that mentees may encounter. While for KOC University this action is new to their institution.
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender (including gender identity); disability; race & ethnicity; nationality; age; family status. Intersectoral dimension; intersectoral (mentors will include people from the industry, business and NGO/CSO spheres).
Intersectoral component	Yes, the external stakeholders are yet to be identified. It is envisioned that some of the mentors will be from business/industry/CSOs.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training materials - Time from mentors and mentees
Audience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mentors (experienced individuals in academia and in the industry, business and NGO/CSO worlds) - Mentees (Doctoral students & ECR)
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gather materials to use in the programme; - Put together the manual for the programme. - Target suitable individuals inside partner institutions to be mentors; - Target suitable individuals from the industry, business and NGO/CSO spheres to be mentors.
Time-frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 13 January 2025 - 9 June 2025: Compile the mentoring programme manual; - July 2025: Launch mentoring programme.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training programmes for mentors and mentees will be developed
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Programme/training manuals for mentors will be produced.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A mentorship programme with inclusivity at its core will be established; - This programme will enhance university-industry relations and intersectorality of academia, thus increasing the total inter-connectivity of research and innovation ecosystems; - The career prospects of early career researchers (doctoral students, post docs, junior faculty) will be developed - regarding - self-confidence, transversal skills and transitions to industry

KU - Action 4	
Action title	Skills Development Program
Key objective	Establishing a skills development program

Thematic area	Gender equality in recruitment and career progression; Gender balance in leadership and decision-making; Work-life balance and organisational culture
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Socio-economic background, Age, Neurodiversity
Intersectoral component	Yes. With this program, the aim is to enhance certain critical skills of especially early career researchers (doctoral students, post docs, junior faculty, etc.). We aim to develop specifically transversal skills and enhance the self-confidence of these women academics for a career switch to industry. There will be certain topics and skills that are critical for certain professional sectors, also there will be trainers/ guests from the industry in this program.
Relevance for data collection	Yes
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two weeks of human work time to develop, implement and analyse the survey - One week of human work time to search for possible stakeholders - One week of human work time to arrange venues and time for workshops - A room for workshop - Budget for catering - Announcement posters to call for participants - E-mail contents for invitation of participants
Audience	Doctoral students and early career researchers.
Activities	Short survey to be conducted in the institution to understand needs for skills development, Network analysis for possible trainers, Programming the dates and venues for meetings, giving at least two workshops on self-presentation skills.
Time-frame	Start date: The program will start in Fall 2024 (first session to be hold in October 2024).
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Survey; - At least two trainings; - A network consists of researchers and trainers (both within academia and industry).
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 10 researchers will be beneficiaries; - At least two workshops will be held; - Evaluation survey result will be available.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhance critical skills like self-presentation skills, negotiation skills, leadership skills, and networking skills for recruitment and career progression; - Each participant will have increased understanding of what skills they need to have and how they can improve these skills.

KU - Action 5	
Action title	Seminar Series on Anti-Feminist Algorithms and AI Bias
Key objective	To raise awareness of misogynist backlash and AI bias on social media among university community
Thematic area	Measures against GBV including sexual harassment
Level of co-design	Open Labs
Intersectional dimensions beyond gender	Gender (including gender identity); disability; race & ethnicity; nationality; age; family status.
Intersectoral component	Yes. This action is closely related to information and communication technologies sector. The seminar series will recruit experts as speakers in the programme, also the professional sector will be engaged in this event and will be invited as audience.
Relevance for data collection	No
Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human time to prepare and give the trainings; - Materials, articles.
Audience	Students & staff & alumni (from industry-intersectorial) & ICT sector actors.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Network analysis for trainer doctoral students, faculty and experts from industry.
Time-frame	Start date: October 2024.
Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased awareness and understanding of GBV; - Increased awareness of how social media contents are displayed and reproduces sexist and discriminatory discourse.
Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least two training sessions will be held; - At least 20 students & 10 non-student community members of university will be beneficiaries.
Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased awareness of GBV, and anti-feminist propaganda; - Each participant will have increased understanding on how new digital technologies enhance sexist, misogynist and anti-equality propaganda.

5 Concluding remarks

This deliverable presented the co-design methodology and the actions designed by the NEXUS implementing partners.

In the Open Labs, 29 actions were co-designed across the nine implementing partner organisations. Between two and six actions were co-designed per partner. Out of these, 16 actions were used to design a portion of the actions that will be implemented by the partners. In one case, one designed action resulted in 2 actions to be implemented due to its particularly wide scope and so as to facilitate implementation ([TUD - Action 4](#) and [TUD - Action 5](#)). Two other actions developed in the Open Labs were shared in the context of the twin trios and adopted for implementation by two other partners ([FredU - Action 2](#), [BZN - Action 2](#), [AGH - Action 2](#); [FredU - Action 3](#), [BZN - Action 4](#), [AGH - Action 3](#)).

In the twin trios, 10 actions were co-designed (two of which coming from the Open Labs, as mentioned above, and eight new actions). All the trios opted for a harmonised approach.

The Open Labs revealed slight challenges with involving external stakeholders and men as participants, confirming that a conscious effort has to be made to promote the diversity of working groups. Important reflections emerged from the Open Labs on inequality grounds and data collection issues, in connection with local legislation and administrative practices. A wide variety of inequality grounds was identified, and they were deemed important to challenge, both at the national and at the institutional level. For instance, grounds of inequality emerged from discussion that had not been included in guidelines and in the project framing so far, such as neurodiversity and job title/seniority, confirming the additional benefit of engaging in discussion and collaborative practices. Some delays occurred in the context of the Open Labs due to organisational issues.

In the twin trios, the preference for a harmonised approach suggests that co-creation and collaboration continue to have a strong impact on the development and implementation of the NEXUS project. Some delays have taken place in the finalisation of actions, pointing to the necessity of follow-up sessions in a co-creation process, going beyond one-off co-creation events. The development of Open Labs actions in the context of the twin trios was particularly interesting, demonstrating the potential for learning and inspiration across parallel co-creation processes.

Overall, additional challenges encountered included the ability to foresee involvement of specific external stakeholders in the actions. Several references to intersectorality in the action design are still at an early stage and will require further planning to ensure a strong intersectoral component. Some of the actions co-designed suggest that utilising a gender+ approach is challenging, due to the risk of reverting to a focus on only one ground of inequality when trying to include further dimensions beyond gender. Further project support could focus on implementing the intersectional gender+ approach in practice. The action portfolio also suggests that, in the frame of a two-year project, it is especially challenging to design actions that promote structural change, for example with the goal of improving data collection processes. Although data

collection has been widely discussed so far in the NEXUS project, several of the actions that have a focus on data collection processes have not been able to plan a structural change.

In terms of the challenges for next steps, one crucial aspect will be the implementation timeline. So far, it appears that proceeding with implementation starting in June 2024 may be unrealistic for some actions, and some are scheduled for 2025. This may affect the punctuality of implementation, monitoring and evaluation activities. In addition, there is variability in the consortium regarding the status of approval from management, with some partners still waiting for approval and budget clarifications to proceed with the selected actions.

Overall, the 45 co-designed actions cover a wide range of thematic areas, from the improvement of work-life balance to countering GBV, and they involve varied action typologies including trainings, surveys and data collection exercises, mentoring schemes, group activities, seminar series, institutional processes and services, and the production of informational guidelines and materials. The portfolio is a solid step towards bridging inclusivity gaps in the nine implementing partner organisations and their respective research and innovation ecosystems.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Email template for inviting external stakeholders to the Open Labs

Dear Stakeholder,

[Brief introduction if stakeholder is new]

We are sending the present email to kindly invite you to participate in the Open Labs we are going to activate in the frame of the [NEXUS project](#).

The NEXUS project (Horizon Europe) aims at co-designing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating innovative actions in nine research organisations and their respective R&I ecosystems. The project wants to bolster institutional change through the development of inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) adopting intersectional and intersectoral perspectives. [Name of implementing partner] is one of the nine research organisations involved in the project.

The co-creation approach is one of the key feature of the project which fosters the role of the external stakeholders belonging to the same R&I environment and materialises with the organisation of the Open Labs, consisting in co-creation workshops that will gather together [Name of implementing partner] internal staff and external stakeholders with the purpose of:

- Presenting the mapping of inequalities identified in [Name of implementing partner] in the previous project activities;
- Discussing on common inequalities;
- Brainstorming of possible solutions to those inequalities also in terms of potential joint actions to be collaborative implemented.

We believe that the participation of representatives of [Name of stakeholder organisation] would greatly benefit the Open Labs, considering the relevance of your institution in [Motivation]/the enduring collaboration in place with [Name of implementing partner].

For this reason we would like to invite to participate in the two Open Labs that will take place on the [Date] and on the [Date] in [Location]. The workshops will take 2-3 hours each. You can register to the Open Labs using the following link: [Link].

Looking forward to meeting you at the Open Labs, we stay at disposal for any question/clarification.

Best regards,

Annex 2. Template for the informed consent of participants in the Open Labs

**TWINNING RESEARCH & INNOVATION INSTITUTIONS TO DESIGN AND
IMPLEMENT INCLUSIVE GEPS**

Information for informed consent (OPEN LABS)

1. Introduction

I am contacting you to kindly invite you to participate in an Open Lab aimed co-designing of inclusive gender equality actions at [Name of institution] for NEXUS, a project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme. The co-creation approach is one of the key features of the project, which fosters the role of internal staff, as well as external stakeholders belonging to the same R&I environment. Open Labs are co-creation workshops which will include:

- A) A presentation and discussion of the mapping of inequalities identified in [Name of institution] in the previous project activities;
- B) Discussion of inequalities that are common to the different organisations represented in the Open Lab
- C) Brainstorming of possible solutions to those inequalities also in terms of potential joint actions to be collaborative implemented.

We believe that your participation would greatly benefit the Open Labs and this is the reason why we are contacting you with this invitation.

2. Participation in the project and right to withdraw

If you consent to participate, you will take part in an Open Lab that will last approximately 180 mins [Edit as appropriate]. Your participation is entirely voluntary. If you decide to participate, you will be invited to read this information sheet and sign it to indicate consent, in print or electronically. You may withdraw your consent and opt out at any time, and you may do so without any explanation and with no consequences for your relation to this institution or to NEXUS project partners. If you wish to exercise your right to withdraw after the Open Lab you can contact the principal investigator (Dr Sara Clavero), with no need to explain why you want to withdraw (contact details below).

3. Procedure

The Open Lab session will be audio-recorded/video-recorded [Delete as appropriate] for the purposes of analysis. The information recorded is confidential, your personal data will be anonymised and no one else except the project research team will have access to the recording, which will be stored in a safe, password protected, place. Once the Open Lab is finished, portions of the recording will be summarised in a report. Your name will not be mentioned in this report. The data will be processed so that unauthorised persons cannot access it.

4. Data protection

All activities carried out in the NEXUS project comply with General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. All personal data collected will be kept secure and no personal data will be kept for longer than necessary for the purposes for which they were collected. Personal data which are no longer required for the purposes of the project will be deleted. You have the right to retract the information you have provided (or remove portions of them) at any time, including your personal data. Only the project team at [Name of institution] will have access to non-anonymised data. Your personal data will be kept confidential and will not be disclosed to any other individual or third parties.

5. Project Results

The results of the project will be disseminated, in compliance with the ethical standards of the scientific community. Reports or any scientific outcomes related to this project will not contain any personal information and you will not be identified or identifiable. We will keep you informed about the project results. These will be reported to the European Commission, as well as in research articles and on digital platforms. Data will only be made publicly available when it is possible to protect the privacy and anonymity of individuals. Some project results and news items will be posted on the project website.

6. Questions and claims

If you have any questions about the project or if you would like to make a complaint on how you have been treated during your participation in the Open Lab, please contact the principal investigator (contact below), who will process it quickly and with utmost care. If you are unsatisfied with the way your complaint is being handled, you can contact the external NEXUS Ethics Advisor.

7. Organisation and Research Funding

NEXUS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101094949

8. Ethical Review Project

The project has passed the ethics review process set by the European Commission and by XXXX [Name of institution].

9. Contact for more information

NEXUS Principal Investigator: Sara Clavero, email: sara.clavero@tudublin.ie

NEXUS Ethics Manager: Adam Molnar, email: adam.molnar@bayzoltan.hu

PARTICIPANT STATEMENT

First, I manifest that I have been invited to participate in the NEXUS project and that I consent voluntarily to participate in an Open Lab.

Second, I confirm that I have read the foregoing information, and I have been properly informed. I have received and understood the information provided about the content, purposes and benefits of this project. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked, have been answered to my satisfaction. Therefore, I am aware that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without the risk of any negative consequences. I understand that the recording of the Open Lab will be kept by the NEXUS project team at [Name of institution] and destroyed at the end of the project/ at the latest on [Delete/specify as appropriate]. I consent to the information I provide being used for research purposes.

Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant

Date (Day/month/year) _____

STATEMENT BY THE RESEARCHER/PERSON TAKING CONSENT

First, I have provided a copy of the project information sheet to the prospective participant, and to the best of my ability have made sure that the participant understands the information provided about the content, purposes and benefits of this project. A copy of this informed consent form has been provided to the participant.

Second, I confirm that the participant has been given an opportunity to ask questions about the project and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the consent is informed and has been given freely and voluntarily.

Name of Researcher _____

Signature of Researcher

Date (Day/month/year) _____

Annex 3. Template for the design of actions

Key objective:**Action's title:**

Impact	
Outcomes	
Audience	
Time-frame	
Activities	
Outputs	
Inputs	
Inclusive dimensions	

Annex 4. Template for reporting activities carried out in the frame of the Open Labs and actions designed

1. Introduction

The present document is aimed at reporting the activities carried out in the frame of the Open Labs as well as in the whole design process.

Please indicate any deviations from the process suggested in the guidelines you adopted.

- Which scenario did you adopt?
- Did the Open Labs take place before the co-design within the trios?

2. Report of the first workshop

Preliminary information

Date:

Number of participants:

Internal stakeholders participating:

Role/Job Position	Number
e.g. dean	3
Human resources department	2

External stakeholders participating:

Stakeholder type	Number	Name of the organisation	Existing collaboration ²
Representatives of companies	3		Yes
Representatives of public bodies/decision makers	2		No
Representatives of CSOs	1		

² Here the existence of a previous collaboration between the stakeholder and the institution is to mention.

Representatives of feminist organisations	1		
Representatives of RPOs/RFOs			

Agenda of the workshop

Please report here the agenda of the first workshop highlighting any changes from the one provided in the T2.3 guidelines.

Time	Activity	Notes

First and second activities - presentation of the project and the GEP

Please report any interesting outcome of the first part of the workshop related to the presentation of the project and of the GEP (if any). Did any question arise? Which one? Can you briefly report them?

Third activity-GE's gaps and inequalities presentation of T2.2 results

Please report how you have structured this section. Did any question arise? Which one? Can you briefly report them?

Fourth activity- Brainstorming on discrimination grounds

Please report the result of the group work. Please remember that in each group it is important to have a note taker, possibly from the project team, or else the role can be undertaken by one of the participants to be provided with a laptop.

How many groups were formed? How many people in each group? Were the group balanced in terms of gender and internal/external stakeholders as well as positions?

Please include one paragraph per group summarising discussions and conclusions and one paragraph on the plenary session.

Discrimination grounds:

- Which discrimination grounds were considered relevant at national level?

- Which minorities were identified are present at institutional level?
- Which discrimination grounds were considered important to be tackled through new actions? Was an agreement reached in each group? What were the most controversial issues raised in the discussion?

Fifth activity- Identifying Key Objectives

Please report the key objectives emerged from the group works categorising them in each thematic area:

Thematic area	Key objective
Work-life balance and organisational culture	
Leadership and decision making	
Recruitment and career progression	
Research and teaching content	
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	
Data collection processes	

3. Report of the meeting of the gep working group with management – scenario one

In this section please report the results of the meeting of the GEP working group taking place between the two workshops of the Open Lab, if the scenario one was adopted.

- Outcomes of the discussion on the validation of the grounds of discrimination identified during the first workshop:
- Key objectives selected and refined, and related actions (at least three overall) identified to meet the key objectives:

Thematic area	Key objectives	Actions
Work-life balance and organisational culture		
Leadership and decision making		
Recruitment and career progression		
Research and teaching content		
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment		

Data collection processes		
---------------------------------	--	--

- Did the GEP working group receive the approval by the management of the institution about the key objectives and the identified actions before the second workshop?

4. Report of the second workshop

Preliminary information

Date:

Number of participants:

Internal stakeholders participating:

Role/Job position	Number	Participating also in the first workshop (yes/no)
e.g. Dean	3	
Human resources officer	2	

Gender composition:

External stakeholders participating:

Role/office	Number	Name of the organisation	Existing collaboration ³	Participating also in the first workshop (yes/no)
Representatives of companies	3		Yes	
Representatives of public bodies/decision makers	2		No	
Representatives of CSOs	1			
Representatives of feminist organisations	1			
Representatives of RPOs/RFOs				

³ Here the existence of a previous collaboration between the stakeholder and the institution is to mention.

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Gender composition:

Please report here the agenda of the second workshop highlighting any changes from the one provided in the T2.3 guidelines.

Time	Activity	Notes

First activity- Presentation of results of the previous workshop

Please report any relevant outcome of first part of the workshop related to the presentation of the results of the previous workshop as well as the key objectives and actions selected by the GEP working group (in case scenario one is adopted).

Second activity- Developing logic models and co-design of actions

Please report the result of this activity.

How many groups were formed? How many people per each group? Were the group balanced in terms of gender and internal/external stakeholders as well as positions?

Please report the outcomes of each group using the template provided. You can either copy-paste the template, fill it using the one provided below or use a simple table.

Group 1

- 1) Action 1
Key objective:
Action's title:

[Insert and fill in template for the design of actions]

- 2) Action 2

[Insert and fill in template for the design of actions]

Please replicate the structure above for each group.

Third activity

Please report the results of the plenary discussion.

Does any action have a collaborative approach?

5. Report of the meeting of the gep working group with management – scenario two

Please report the outcome of the meeting within the GEP working group after the two workshops.

- Which actions co-designed within the Open Labs have been validated by the GEP working group? Were such actions approved by the management of the institution?

6. Actions designed and ready to be implemented

In this section each partner will report the five (or more) actions that they commit to implement in the frame of the NEXUS project as a result of the co-design process carried out in the frame of the Open Labs, of the trios and internally at institution level.

It is important to remind that each institution has to design and implement minimum five actions each, three of them to be co-design within the trios. Two actions have to have a strong collaborative component. The design of the five actions will need to be finalised by the **first week of May 2024**.

Please report all the actions designed that will be implemented. You can either copy-paste the template, fill it using the one provided below or use a simple table.

Actions co-designed within the trios

- Did the co-design within the trios take place after the Open Labs?
- Did the actions co-design within the trios originate from the Open Labs, as a result of the second workshop?

Please report here below the actions co-designed within the trios:

Action 1

Key objective:

Action's title:

Intersectoral component: Y/N (if yes please specify which external stakeholders are involved and with which roles)

- Was the action jointly co-designed by the trio?
- If yes, was it fully or partly designed within the trio?
- In case it was partly designed within the trio, which parts were designed/adjusted internally by the GEP working group?
- Will the action be implemented by all components of the trio?

[Insert and fill in template for the design of actions]

Alternately

Please replicate it for the other two actions designed within the trios.

Other actions co-designed by the institution

Action 4

Key objective:

Action's title:

Intersectoral component: Y/N (if yes please specify which external stakeholders are involved and with which roles)

- Was the action initially co-designed within the Open Labs?

[Insert and fill in template for the design of actions]

Please replicate it for each other action co-designed.

Annex 5. Template for reporting the first study visit

The present document is aimed at reporting the activities carried out in the frame of the first trio's study visit.

Trio's composition/number:

Study visit's day and time:

Study visit's agenda

Please report the agenda of the study visit indicating any variations from the one suggested in the guidelines.

Time	Activity	Notes

Please include some pictures of the event.

Study visits participants (of both the hosting organisation and the guests):

Partner	Name	Gender	Role/position

Report of the different activities taking place in the study visit:

- Hosting institution tour: please provide details about this activity. Which areas of the institutions involved? Which people?

- Institutions' good practices on GE & inclusion: please report the good practices that were presented and the main highlights of the discussion

- External stakeholders' good practices on GE & inclusion: please report number and type of stakeholders participating and the good practices shared as well as the main highlights of the discussion

- Exploring guests' institutions and good practices: please report what was shared during this activity, which questions emerged from the internal/externals stakeholders and the students

- Joint actions' co-design: please report the result of the co-design activity within the trios. In particular, report which approach has been adopted (harmonised, flexible or mixed approach) and indicate the result of the co-design for each action designed using the template below (you can also report the contents of the different components in a table). Please consider that the finalised versions of the actions will be reported by each partner in the overall report attached to T2.3 guidelines, while here only the result of the co-design in the trio has to be reported.

Also please report the result of the mutual updated related to the co-design taking place at the institutional level as well as the discussion around how to coordinate the different co-design levels.

Action 1

Name of the action:

Thematic area:

Key objective addressed:

Common action within the trio: yes/no

If it is a common action, please indicate if any parts will be adapted by each institution individually

[Insert and fill in template for the design of actions]

Please report any issues/challenges that emerged when designing these actions as well as misalignments among partners.

Please replicate for all the actions co-designed.

- Learning needs brainstorming: please report the results of the activity of brainstorming in terms of learning needs and challenges emerged.
- Next steps: please highlight the next steps of the collaboration in terms of periodic calls and the following study visit.